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Master Thesis

Dynamic mode decomposition for parametric fluid flow modeling

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Abstract

The dynamics of fluid flows vary significantly across operating conditions, and capturing these parameter-dependent changes remains a central challenge in reduced-order modelling. Parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition (pDMD), as implemented in PyDMD, provides a data-driven framework for this task, yet its accuracy and stability degrade in non-linear or noisy regimes. This work develops and validates an improved pDMD algorithm. The method is first assessed on the laminar cylinder-flow example, which also served as the reference case for evaluating the pDMD implementation in PyDMD, and is subsequently extended to transonic airfoil stall conditions with varying angle of attack. Results show that the proposed method, based on the mode-realigned pointwise interpolation (MRPWI) framework, resolves the structural deficiencies of PyDMD's approach, producing smooth spectral variation across parameters, accurate mode interpolation, and stable long-term reconstructions even at unseen operating points. In addition, the method demonstrates robustness to noise, maintaining consistent spectral alignment and reconstruction quality across increasing noise levels. For the airfoil case, the method successfully captures the dominant buffet mode, its harmonics, and the associated shock-oscillation dynamics despite the limited number of training parameters. These findings demonstrate that enforcing spectral consistency and interpolating aligned DMD quantities provides a reliable foundation for parametric reduced-order modelling of non-linear flows, offering a promising basis for future extensions to multi-parameter applications.

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Table of Symbols

Latin Symbols	Units	Meaning
$a_j(t)$	-	j -th POD modal coefficient
A	-	Linear mapping operator
$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$	-	Reduced DMD operator
C_L	-	Lift coefficient
\mathbf{b}_0	-	Initial DMD modal amplitude vector
$E(r)$	-	Cumulative POD energy fraction
E_j	-	Energy of POD mode j
\tilde{f}	-	Non-dimensional frequency
$l_i(\mu^*)$	-	Lagrange interpolation weight
N_p	-	Stencil size for interpolation
\mathbf{Q}_j	-	Orthonormal basis of a j -mode sub-space
Re	-	Reynolds number
s_j	-	j -th DMD continuous-time eigenvalue
St	-	Strouhal number
S	-	Diagonal matrix of continuous-time eigenvalues
T	s	Total physical simulation time
t_n	-	Time instant of snapshot n
\tilde{t}	-	Non-dimensional time
U_∞	m/s	Freestream velocity used for non-dimensionalisation
U	-	Matrix of left singular vectors
V	-	Matrix of right singular vectors

\mathbf{W}	-	Matrix of eigenvectors of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$
\mathbf{X}	-	Snapshot matrix
$\tilde{\mathbf{X}}$	-	Projected snapshot matrix
\mathcal{X}_1	-	Concatenated snapshot matrix over all training parameters
\mathcal{X}_2	-	Matrix of forecasted reduced states for all training parameters
\mathbf{Y}	-	Shifted snapshot matrix
\mathbf{x}_n	-	Snapshot vector at time t_n

Greek Symbols	Units	Meaning
α	deg	Angle of attack
γ_k	-	k -th principal angle between subspaces
δ_x	-	Local noise-scaling coefficient
$\varepsilon_{\text{eig}}(j)$	-	Relative interpolation error of eigenvalue j
$\varepsilon_{\text{mode}}(j)$	-	Relative interpolation error of mode j
ε_{rel}	-	Relative L^2 reconstruction error
$\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{rel}}$	-	Mean relative L^2 reconstruction error
η	%	Prescribed noise level
ϑ	-	Arbitrary global phase shift of a DMD mode
λ_j	-	j -th DMD discrete-time eigenvalue
$\mathbf{\Lambda}$	-	Diagonal matrix of DMD eigenvalues
μ	-	Continuous parameter

μ_i	-	Training parameter
μ^*	-	Unseen/test parameter
ρ	1/s	Growth/decay rate of continuous eigenvalue
σ_j	-	j -th singular value
Σ	-	Diagonal matrix of singular values
$\varphi(\cdot, \cdot)$	-	Pseudo-angle between two complex vectors
φ_j	-	Pseudo-angle for mode j
ω	1/s	Oscillation frequency of continuous eigenvalue
ϕ_j	-	j -th DMD mode
Φ	-	Matrix of DMD modes
ψ_j	-	j -th POD mode

Indices	Meaning
c	Closest neighbour in the stencil set
i	Parameter index
j	Mode index
k	Principal-angle index
m	Number of spatial degrees of freedom
n	Snapshot (time) index
N	Total number of snapshots
p	Number of training parameters
r	Truncation rank

R Total number of nonzero singular values ($\min(m, N)$)

Other Symbols	Units	Meaning
*	-	Untested or unseen parameter
†	-	Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse operator
\mathcal{I}	-	Interpolation operator
$\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$	-	Standard normal Gaussian random variable
\mathcal{P}	-	Set of training parameters
\mathcal{R}	-	High–Reynolds training set for transitional regime analysis
\mathcal{S}_{N_p}	-	Parameter stencil of N_p
\mathcal{T}	-	Set of discrete time indices

Acronyms	Meaning
DMD	Dynamic Mode Decomposition
MRPWI	Mode-Realigned Pointwise Interpolation
pDMD	Parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition
POD	Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
PODI	Proper Orthogonal Decomposition with Interpolation
ParametricDMD	Parametric DMD implementation in PyDMD

PyDMD	Python library for Dynamic Mode Decomposition
RBF	Radial Basis Function
rEPI	Reduced Eigenpair Interpolation
rKOI	Reduced Koopman Operator Interpolation
SALSA	Strain-Adaptive Linear Spalart-Allmaras

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

In fluid dynamics, the understanding of complex fluid flows is critical for designing, modelling and optimization of complex shapes and geometries e.g., ship hull design, fighter jet body. There are currently several numerical simulation schemes available for solving the equations governing fluid flow i.e., Navier-Stokes equation, such as, RANS (Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes) which is an Industry standard for solving complex flows. LES (Large Eddy Simulation) resolves large turbulent structures, which is good for detailed analysis of unsteady flows. DNS (Direct Numerical Simulation) is a method that resolves all scales, which has the highest accuracy but it is quite expensive in terms of the computational cost. And for modelling the dynamic behaviour of fluid flows across a range of operating conditions is a central challenge and often require accurate yet efficient representations of unsteady flows under varying physical parameters. These above mentioned traditional full-order models, offer high fidelity but are computationally expensive—especially when used for parametric studies, control design, or real-time prediction. To overcome these limitations, Reduced Order Modelling (ROM) techniques have emerged as powerful tools for extracting low-dimensional representations from high-fidelity simulations or experimental data. ROMs, such as Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) [26, 38] and Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) [37], significantly reduce the computational complexity of numerical simulations while preserving essential dynamical features. For example, the reduction of system model's degrees of freedom or the number of variables while maintaining the computational accuracy which makes it feasible compared to running large scale simulations for design and optimization. Parametric Reduced Order Models (PROMs) have also been successfully applied in a wide range of engineering fields. In aerodynamics, PROMs enable efficient exploration of flight envelopes by varying parameters such as Reynolds number, Mach number, and angle of attack [6]. In structural mechanics, they allow vibration and stability studies under varying material or geometric properties [44]. PROMs have also been used in turbomachinery and naval engineering for design optimization across wide parametric ranges [31], and in biomedical applications such as cardiovascular flow modelling where patient-specific parameters are critical [27]. These examples highlight the versatility of PROMs in handling parametric studies that would otherwise be computationally prohibitive.

Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) has become a widely used data-driven tool for analysing unsteady flows. It provides a spectral decomposition that identifies dominant frequencies and coherent structures, which makes it particularly suitable for studying vortex shedding, shear-layer instabilities, and other flow phenomena governed by coherent dynamics. Its theoretical foundations were strengthened through connections to Koopman operator theory [30, 43]. Several extensions

improved its robustness in noisy or weakly non-linear regimes, including regularized DMD [15], higher-order DMD [7], optimized DMD [4], and physics-informed variants [5, 21, 46]. These developments established DMD as a flexible and scalable framework for analysing high-dimensional unsteady flows and extracting dominant dynamical features from complex fluid-mechanical datasets.

Building on these foundations, Parametric DMD (pDMD) was introduced to model how DMD quantities vary with operating parameters such as Reynolds number, Mach number, or geometric configuration. Early work by [32] proposed amplitude correction for transient regimes and a stacked snapshot formulation that aggregates data from multiple parameters into a single augmented matrix. This approach is effective for thermo-acoustic bifurcations but requires a shared temporal grid and becomes increasingly expensive as the number of parameters grows. Later workflows [9, 41] combined DMD with interpolation in a POD space and with parameter-space reduction. These methods demonstrated that non-intrusive reduced-order models can accelerate design studies in aerodynamics and hydrodynamics, although their accuracy remains sensitive to the density and distribution of the training samples.

More systematic formulations were introduced in [18]. The authors compared stacked snapshots with reduced eigenpair interpolation (rEPI) and reduced Koopman-operator interpolation (rKOI). These methods compute DMD independently at each parameter and interpolate either eigenpairs or reduced operators. They avoid the shared-eigenvalue constraint and scale more favourably with parameter dimension. The study evaluates these strategies on non-linear diffusion-dominated PDEs rather than fluid-mechanical systems, but the methodological conclusions are general: the accuracy of both interpolation approaches depends on the smoothness of the parameter-to-operator map. When this mapping varies rapidly or is insufficiently resolved by the training set, the interpolated operators can lose consistency. This limitation also arises in parameter-dependent fluid flows, where spectral behaviour may change abruptly across the parameter domain.

Several non-intrusive approaches have also been explored for fluid-mechanical applications. The KNN-DMD [11] method uses nearest-neighbour regression to interpolate DMD reconstructions across parameter space and performs well for laminar cylinder flows. RBF interpolation within the DMD framework [39] generates synthetic snapshots at new parameters before applying DMD. Interpolation on a POD-DMD manifold [16] uses subspace geometry to recover parameter-dependent oscillatory behaviour in flows with Hopf bifurcations. Complementary work [25] examined how sampling range, resolution, and observable choice influence DMD's spectral fidelity in turbulent wakes, highlighting the importance of preprocessing and truncation strategies for stable Koopman approximations in fluid systems.

A complete and practically usable pDMD pipeline was introduced in [3]. It combines a global POD basis, temporal forecasting through DMD, and interpolation of POD coefficients across parameter space. This formulation was implemented in the `PYDMD` library [19], enabling reproducible para-

metric prediction for fluid flows. More recent work [1] applied multi-linear interpolation of DMD operators to thermal channel flows. The method is fast and non-intrusive but depends on snapshot ordering and assumes locally linear parameter–state relationships, which may not hold in flows with strong non-linearities or sharp parameter-dependent transitions.

Further developments in interpolation driven extensions were presented in [10]. This work introduced subspace angle interpolation (SAI), Grassmann manifold interpolation (GMI), and mode re-aligned pointwise interpolation (MRPWI) as three strategies for interpolating complex-valued, non orthonormal DMD modes. In their framework, eigenvalues are interpolated using Lagrange polynomials, while MRPWI also applies Lagrange interpolation pointwise to the spatial modes after enforcing a consistent mode alignment. These methods improved accuracy and modal consistency for the canonical cylinder-flow benchmark. Among them, MRPWI stands out due to its simplicity, low computational cost, and good scalability, which makes it attractive for fluid-mechanical applications. Its performance still depends on reliable modal correspondence across parameters, so errors in mode pairing or spectral ordering can influence the reconstructed dynamics.

Despite the breadth of existing approaches, parametric DMD remains challenging when applied to fluid-mechanical systems. Most formulations rely on assumptions of smooth spectral variation, consistent modal correspondence, and stable interpolation across parameter-domain conditions, assumptions that frequently break down in flows where the underlying dynamics undergo rapid qualitative changes. In regimes involving bifurcations, frequency shifts, mode coalescence, or strongly non-linear transients, the Koopman spectrum may vary non-smoothly with the parameter, causing eigenvalues to reorder or drift in ways that violate the continuity required for reliable interpolation. Under such circumstances, even small inconsistencies in modal alignment can propagate through the reconstruction process, leading to inaccurate predictions at unseen operating conditions and a loss of physical interpretability. These limitations underscore the need for systematic evaluation of existing pDMD formulations and for more robust strategies capable of maintaining modal correspondence, spectral consistency, and predictive accuracy across parameter-dependent flows.

1.2 Objectives and scope of work

The objective of this work is to evaluate and validate the existing `ParametricDMD` method introduced in [3] and implemented in the open-source `PyDMD` library [8]. Although `PyDMD` provides a consolidated and reproducible framework for Dynamic Mode Decomposition, the performance, robustness, and physical consistency of its `ParametricDMD` class have not yet been systematically assessed for fluid-mechanical applications. This study therefore focuses on analysing how accurately the baseline method reconstructs, forecasts, and interpolates flow dynamics across varying operating conditions.

The evaluation is carried out on the canonical test case of laminar flow past a cylinder, with particular attention to modal accuracy, long-term stability, and sensitivity to noise. This provides a controlled setting for identifying the strengths and limitations of the baseline `ParametricDMD` formulation when applied to parameter-dependent unsteady flows.

Building on insights from the assessment and prior literature, an improved pDMD algorithm is developed by integrating optimized-DMD principles [46] and adopting the mode-realigned pointwise interpolation (MRPWI) strategy from [10] to achieve robust and physically consistent interpolation at unseen parameters. The enhanced method is implemented within the `flowTorch` framework to enable modular experimentation and reproducible evaluation. Its performance is validated on two representative flow problems. The laminar cylinder wake and a transonic airfoil undergoing high-speed stall with varying angle of attack. The resulting analysis provides a comprehensive analysis of the improved formulations and assesses its generalization capability across the considered flow regimes.

To support transparency and reproducibility, all code and experimental resources used in this study are provided in the accompanying open-source repository [2].

2 Theoretical Foundations

2.1 Fundamentals of Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

The Proper Orthogonal Decomposition provides an optimal low-dimensional representation of high-dimensional flow data by identifying the most energetic spatial structures of the system. The basic idea of POD is to represent complex systems in a reduced space using a small number of modes ψ_j that capture the majority of the system's variance or energy. Figure (2.1) illustrates the general workflow of the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition.

Figure 2.1: General schema of the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition.

POD is applied to snapshots obtained from experiments or numerical simulations, where each snapshot represents the system's state at a specific time. We consider a dataset consisting of N snapshots, each of dimension m , where m denotes the number of scalar degrees of freedom in the state vector. This state may include multiple physical fields (e.g., the stacked components $[u_x, u_y, p]$ evaluated at all spatial points). The snapshot matrix is then defined as $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times N}$,

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & \cdots & | \\ \mathbf{x}_1 & \mathbf{x}_2 & \cdots & \mathbf{x}_N \\ | & | & \cdots & | \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

where each column \mathbf{x}_n ($n = 1, \dots, N$) is a vector that represents the instantaneous state of the system at time t_n and usually, $m \gg N$ (more spatial points than time observables).

We then apply the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) to \mathbf{X} ,

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^\top \quad (2.2)$$

which gives $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ (left Singular vectors) an orthogonal matrix that contains the POD modes ψ_j (spatial patterns). $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times N}$ (Singular values) a diagonal with singular values σ_j which are ordered $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_R \geq 0$, where $R = \min(m, N)$. $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ (right Singular vectors) which represents the temporal dynamics or coefficients v_j associated with each mode.

In POD, the energy or variance captured by the j -th mode is proportional to the square of its singular value σ_j^2 ,

$$E_j = \sigma_j^2 \quad (2.3)$$

To reduce the dimensionality of the system, we must choose a truncation rank r ($r \ll N$) to capture the cumulative energy content. This cumulative energy content $E(r)$ is defined as,

$$E(r) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^r \sigma_j^2}{\sum_{j=1}^R \sigma_j^2} \quad (2.4)$$

The rank r is chosen such that $E \approx 0.99$ (99% of the system's energy is captured) Once the rank r is determined, truncating the matrices to keep only the first r columns/rows gives,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{X}} \approx \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{\Sigma}_r \mathbf{V}_r^\top \quad (2.5)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$ contains the first r POD modes, $\mathbf{\Sigma}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ the $r \times r$ diagonal with dominant singular values and $\mathbf{V}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times N}$ the first r temporal trajectories.

While POD provides an optimal orthogonal basis in space that captures the second-order statistics of the data, it does not explicitly resolve temporal dynamics. The decomposition is based on spatial orthogonality of the modes ψ_j and their ordering by energy σ_j^2 , meaning that the modes are ranked according to variance content rather than frequency. This spatial focus distinguishes POD from Dynamic Mode Decomposition, which applies directly to the ordered sequence of snapshots $\mathbf{x}_{n,i}$ taken at discrete times t_n , and orthogonalizes them in time, thereby isolating distinct temporal frequencies through its eigenvalues λ and associated DMD modes ϕ .

2.2 Fundamentals of Dynamic Mode Decomposition

The algorithm begins with a sequence of N snapshots of the state vector $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times N}$. We consider a set $\mathcal{T} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ of discrete time instants which are equidistant in time which will be referred to as *tested* or *known* time instants.

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N] \quad (2.6)$$

We arrange the snapshots into two shifted matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} , both $\in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (N-1)}$.

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N-1}], \quad \mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{x}_3, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N] \quad (2.7)$$

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \mathbf{x}_1 & \mathbf{x}_2 & \cdots & \mathbf{x}_{N-1} \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \mathbf{x}_2 & \mathbf{x}_3 & \cdots & \mathbf{x}_N \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.8)$$

where each $\mathbf{x}_n \in \mathbb{R}^m$ represents the state of the system at time t_n .

Figure 2.2: General schema of the Dynamic Mode Decomposition.

The assumption is that there exists a linear mapping \mathbf{A} such that,

$$\mathbf{Y} \approx \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} \quad (2.9)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times m}$ is a high dimensional operator we want to characterize.

In principle, the eigenpairs (λ_j, ϕ_j) of the operator \mathbf{A} provide the spectral ingredients of the system's state: the eigenvalues λ_j determine growth/decay and oscillation rates, while the eigenvectors ϕ_j define the associated spatial structures. These spectral quantities describe how coherent features evolve in time and are therefore the objects DMD seeks to recover, however, this operator's \mathbf{A} computation is numerically prohibitive for large m even when a governing model exists, the dynamics may be effectively non-linear (so a finite linear operator is only an approximation), and measurements are contaminated by noise and incomplete sampling.

So, instead a truncated SVD is performed on \mathbf{X} to find a low-rank subspace for rank r ,

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{\Sigma}_r \mathbf{V}_r^T \quad (2.10)$$

with $\mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times r}$ the first r left singular vectors (POD modes), $\mathbf{\Sigma}_r \in \mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$ the r largest singular values and $\mathbf{V}_r \in \mathbb{C}^{(N-1) \times r}$ the first r right singular vectors.

Substituting Equation (2.10) into (2.11) and projecting the mapping \mathbf{A} onto the column space of \mathbf{U}_r yields the reduced operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$,

$$\mathbf{A} \approx \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{X}^\dagger = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{V}_r\mathbf{\Sigma}_r^{-1}\mathbf{U}_r^T \quad (2.11)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{U}_r = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{V}_r \mathbf{\Sigma}_r^{-1} \quad (2.12)$$

where \dagger is the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse operator [29]. The reduced operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ is a surrogate that is computationally tractable and numerically stable. It represents the dynamics of the system constrained to the most energetic spatial structures. Since $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ and \mathbf{A} share the same non-zero eigenvalues, this reduced operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ captures the dominant behaviour of the full operator \mathbf{A} on the data subspace spanned by the leading left singular vectors \mathbf{U}_r . Consequently, its spectral properties provide low-dimensional approximations to the dominant spectral features of the full dynamics. So, we solve the eigenvalue problem of the reduced operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{\Lambda} \quad (2.13)$$

which yields $\Lambda \in \mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$ DMD eigenvalues λ_j as $\text{diag}(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_r)$ which are complex and capture frequency and growth/decay of each spatial mode (DMD mode) ϕ_j . The eigenvectors $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{r \times r}$ describe the dominant dynamics of the reduced operator, and their columns correspond to the DMD modes.

Then to obtain physically interpretable DMD modes ϕ_j in the original m -dimensional space, we compute the DMD modes as [43],

$$\Phi = \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{V}_r \Sigma_r^{-1} \mathbf{W} \quad (2.14)$$

Each column of $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times r}$ is a DMD mode ϕ_j , which represents a coherent spatial structure oscillating at a frequency which is determined by its associated eigenvalues λ_j . The system's state can be represented as a linear combination of these modes. By projecting the initial condition x_0 (snapshot at $t = 0$) onto the DMD basis, we determine the initial modal amplitudes $b_0 = \Phi^\dagger x_0$. The reconstruction of snapshot sequence is then expressed by evolving these amplitudes through time according to the time dynamics,

$$x_n = \Phi \Lambda^n \Phi^\dagger x_0 = \Phi \Lambda^n b_0 \quad (2.15)$$

Consequently, there are virtually no constraints on $n \in \mathbb{N}$, therefore it is possible to use Equation (2.15) to extrapolate the snapshot x_n for $n > N$, and we can also predict the behavior of the function of interest outside the *tested* or *training* time window (i.e., forecasting), but, with some uncertainty as the state of the system at any time step k is reconstructed through the evolution of initial condition x_0 forward in time.

$$x_k = \Phi \Lambda^k \Phi^\dagger x_0 \quad (2.16)$$

In summary, Dynamic Mode Decomposition offers a powerful data-driven framework for extracting coherent structures and their associated temporal dynamics directly from snapshot data. Its applicability to both numerical and experimental datasets, together with its compatibility with numerous extensions and variants, makes DMD a versatile and widely used tool for reduced-order modelling and flow analysis.

2.2.1 Parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition

The DMD framework presented in the previous section extracts coherent structures and their temporal behaviour from a sequence of snapshots for a single operating condition. Many practical systems, however, exhibit dynamics that vary with an external parameter μ (for example Reynolds number, inflow velocity, geometric configuration, or a control parameter). Applying classical DMD independently at each sampled parameter value produces a set of isolated decompositions with no

intrinsic relation between them and no straightforward way to predict the system at an unseen parameter. Parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition (pDMD) extends the DMD paradigm by embedding the parameter dependence directly into the decomposition so that the spectral components themselves become functions of the parameter μ .

Figure 2.3: General schema of Parametric DMD, inspired by [3].

The essence of pDMD is that we treat snapshots \mathbf{x}_n of both time and parameter,

$$\mathbf{x}_n(\mu_i) \equiv \mathbf{x}(t_n, \mu_i), \quad \mu_i \in \mathcal{P} \quad (2.17)$$

where $\mathcal{P} = \{\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_p\}$ represents the set of p training parameters. As illustrated in Figure (2.3), we begin by collecting snapshot matrices $\mathbf{X}(\mu_i)$ and $\mathbf{Y}(\mu_i)$ for each training parameter as defined in Equation (2.7). For each μ_{i_r} , a local reduced-order model is constructed. Following the SVD-based projection and eigendecomposition detailed in Section (2.2), we obtain parameter-dependent spectral components: the reduced operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_i)$, DMD eigenvalues $\Lambda(\mu_i)$, and the lifted DMD modes $\Phi(\mu_i)$.

The parametric reconstruction of the system state for an *untested* or *unseen* parameter μ^* is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{x}_n(\mu^*) = \Phi(\mu^*) \mathbf{\Lambda}^n(\mu^*) \Phi^\dagger(\mu^*) \mathbf{x}_0(\mu^*) \approx \sum_{j=1}^r \phi_j(\mu^*) \lambda_j^k(\mu^*) b_{0,j}(\mu^*) \quad (2.18)$$

To enable prediction at an *unseen* parameter value μ^* , pDMD requires an interpolation framework to bridge the discrete training samples. Various strategies exist to construct a continuous surrogate mapping \mathcal{I} :

$$\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{P} \rightarrow \{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu), \Phi(\mu), \Lambda(\mu), \mathbf{b}_0(\mu)\} \quad (2.19)$$

In practice, this mapping can be achieved through different methodologies, such as Proper Orthogonal Decomposition with Interpolation (PODI) [3,41], where the modal coefficients are interpolated. The stacked pDMD approach [32], where they interpolate the DMD modes ϕ and initial amplitudes \mathbf{b}_0 to evaluate the system at a new parameter μ^* . Another strategy is the reduced eigenpair interpolation (rEPI) [18], in which the resulting eigenvalues λ , modes ϕ , and amplitudes \mathbf{b} from the reduced system are interpolated across the parameter domain. The reduced operators $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_i)$ are used in reduced Koopman operator interpolation (rKOI) [18] method. These operator obtained at each parameter are interpolated first, and the eigenpairs at a new parameter are recovered from the eigendecomposition of this interpolated operator.

2.2.2 PyDMD: Partitioned ParametricDMD

In the underlying work, we evaluate the existing implementation of the partitioned variant of Parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition (pDMD), as described [3] and a dedicated pDMD class in the open-source Python library PyDMD [19] as ParamDMD. The remainder of this work this method will be referred to as ParametricDMD and the subsection follows the description of the methodology as presented in the original work.

Figure (2.4) presents the schematic pipeline of the partitioned ParametricDMD methodology, which is organized into two phases: an offline phase for training and operator construction, and an online phase for forecasting of the trained parameter μ_i and then interpolating for the unknown parameter μ^* .

Offline Phase For each $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$, we collect N high-fidelity snapshots $\mathbf{x}_n(\mu) \equiv \mathbf{x}(t_n, \mu_i) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ at equispaced time instants $t_n \in \mathcal{T} = \{t_1, \dots, t_N\}$, resulting in a total of $N_p = p \times N$ snapshots. These snapshots are grouped into parameter-specific columns $\mathbf{X}^{\mu_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times N}$, and a concatenated form of the full snapshot matrix is created by collecting all parameters together as,

$$\mathcal{X}_1 = [\mathbf{X}^{\mu_1} \ \mathbf{X}^{\mu_2} \ \dots \ \mathbf{X}^{\mu_p}] \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times N_p} \quad (2.20)$$

We then apply Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) to \mathcal{X}_1 for an optimal data reduction truncated by first r modes, yielding the reduced basis $\mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$. Each parameter-specific snapshot

Figure 2.4: Schematic pipeline of the Partitioned ParametricDMD methodology, inspired by [3].

matrix is then projected onto this basis,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{X}}^{\mu_i} := \mathbf{U}_r^\top \mathbf{X}^{\mu_i} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & & | \\ \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_1^{\mu_i} & \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_2^{\mu_i} & \dots & \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_N^{\mu_i} \\ | & | & & | \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times N} \quad (2.21)$$

Which gives us the POD modal coefficients in the matrix form $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}^{\mu_i}$ corresponding to the snapshots for each parameter stored in \mathcal{X}_1 . Then Dynamic Mode Decomposition is performed independently on the coefficients for each parameter μ_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, on the shifted matrices $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}^{\mu_i}, \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{\mu_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times (N-1)}$ which results from taking $N-1$ columns of $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}^{\mu_i}$ as in the standard DMD method (2.2) then the corresponding operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{\mu_i} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ is approximated such that $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{\mu_i} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{\mu_i} \tilde{\mathbf{X}}^{\mu_i}$.

Online Phase The online phase first predicts the POD coefficients at a future time t^k (where $k > N$) for training parameters μ_i and then interpolates for the *unseen* parameter μ^* . After forecasting, the algorithm then collects the reduced states into the matrix,

$$\mathcal{X}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} | & \cdots & | \\ \tilde{x}(t_k, \mu_1) & \cdots & \tilde{x}(t_k, \mu_p) \\ | & \cdots & | \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times p} \quad (2.22)$$

Where each row of \mathcal{X}_2 represents the forecasted POD coefficient and the column gives each realization of the parametric system used for training. These reduced quantities are used to learn the parametric dependence of the system and interpolation is performed directly on these reduced coordinates $\tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu_i}$. In other words, the regressor learns how the POD coefficients at time t^k vary with the parameter μ_i which is similar to Proper Orthogonal Decomposition with Interpolation (PODI) [9, 41]. A regression map $\mathcal{I}_{t^k} : \mathcal{P} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^r$ is then trained on the pairs $(\mu_i, \tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu_i})$ for $i = 1, \dots, p$, using a Radial Basis Function (RBF) interpolator. Evaluating this map at the *unseen* parameter μ^* yields the predicted reduced state,

$$\tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu^*} = \mathcal{I}_{t^k}(\mu^*) \quad (2.23)$$

and the full-order *unknown* parameter μ^* is finally reconstructed using the POD basis.

$$\mathbf{x}_{t^k}^{\mu^*} = \mathbf{U}_r \tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu^*} \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (2.24)$$

The sequence defines the online stage of the partitioned ParametricDMD: first, each training parameter is advanced in time using its corresponding reduced operator; second, the resulting states are assembled and interpolated across the parameter space; finally, the predicted reduced state for the unseen parameter is lifted back to the full dimension through the POD basis.

Algorithm 1: \mathcal{P}_{DMD} : Partitioned ParametricDMD [3, 19]

Input: Snapshot matrices $\{\mathbf{X}^{\mu_i}\}_{i=1}^p$, time grid \mathcal{T} , number of POD modes r

Output: Predicted full-order state $\mathbf{x}_{t^k}^{\mu^*}$

Concatenate snapshots: $\mathcal{X}_1 = [\mathbf{X}^{\mu_1}, \dots, \mathbf{X}^{\mu_p}]$;

Compute POD basis: $\mathbf{U}_r \leftarrow \text{POD}(\mathcal{X}_1)$;

for $i = 1$ to p **do**

Project snapshots: $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}^{\mu_i} = \mathbf{U}_r^\top \mathbf{X}^{\mu_i}$;

Form DMD matrices: $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_1^{\mu_i}, \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{\mu_i}$;

Fit reduced operator: $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{\mu_i}$;

Forecast reduced states: $\tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu_i} = (\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{\mu_i})^k \tilde{x}_{t_N}^{\mu_i}$;

Train regressor \mathcal{I}_{t^k} on $(\mu_i, \tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu_i})$;

Evaluate at μ^* : $\tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu^*} = \mathcal{I}_{t^k}(\mu^*)$;

Reconstruct full state: $\mathbf{x}_{t^k}^{\mu^*} = \mathbf{U}_r \tilde{x}_{t^k}^{\mu^*}$;

3 Baseline evaluation of existing pDMD

3.1 Problem setup and model configuration

For the evaluation of the baseline implementation of pDMD, *ParametricDMD* [3, 19] is chosen, and we consider the two-dimensional flow past a circular cylinder, a standard benchmark for reduced-order modelling and parametric studies [28]. The simulation setup used in this work are taken from the openly available repository [45]. The simulation setup was provided as part of this dataset and is used here without modification. We numerically solve the incompressible Navier–Stokes equations governing the flow around a circular cylinder.

Figure 3.1: Flow domain for laminar flow past a cylinder.

The computational domain Ω consists of a 2D channel containing a cylinder of diameter $D = 0.10 \text{ m}$ placed two diameters downstream of the inlet, as illustrated in Figure (3.1). The inflow boundary condition is prescribed as a parabolic velocity profile, while enforcing no-slip at the channel walls. No-slip conditions are also applied on the cylinder surface, and a convective boundary condition is imposed at the outlet to allow vortical structures to exit the domain without reflection. The parameter μ controls the horizontal component of the inflow velocity (the vertical component is set to zero) and thereby the Reynolds number, $Re = U_\infty D / \nu$, where $\nu = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ is the kinematic viscosity and U_∞ denotes the freestream velocity (in m/s). By varying U_∞ , one directly controls the Reynolds number and thus the onset and strength of vortex shedding.

To focus the reduced-order modelling on the dynamically relevant portion of the flow, a spatial mask is applied to the discretized domain, as shown in Figure (3.2). The mask selects all grid points whose coordinates lie in the rectangular region $[0.1, 0.75] \times [-1, 1]$, thereby isolating the wake region behind the cylinder while excluding the upstream portion of the channel. The masked domain contains

5746 grid points and forms the basis for all evaluations of the `ParametricDMD` implementation. This selective sampling ensures that the reduced models emphasize coherent structures associated with vortex shedding across the parameter space.

Figure 3.2: Masked region used for reduced order modelling (ROM).

Finally, we run the simulation for a total physical time of $T = 20.0\text{s}$ with a time step of $\Delta t = 0.01$, which results in 2001 snapshots of the velocity field at equispaced time instants, and all computations are performed using the open-source finite-volume framework `OpenFOAM`.

3.2 ParametricDMD model configuration

Our focus is restricted to the vanilla DMD formulation within the partitioned framework, without using the noise-tolerant variants, or higher-order extensions and eigenvalue λ stabilization [3] before interpolation. The focus is on assessing the baseline implementation of the class when applied. The *training* parameter set \mathcal{P} is chosen as $Re = \{100, 110, 120, 130, 140, 150, 160, 180, 190, 200\}$ (Figure (3.3)),

Figure 3.3: Training and test parameters for pDMD

while the *untested* or *unseen* parameter is selected $Re^* = 170$, which is deliberately off-center to pro-

vide a more challenging test case. The selected Reynolds numbers lie within the two-dimensional laminar vortex-shedding regime of the cylinder flow, ensuring that the dynamics remain periodic, coherent, and strictly laminar throughout the training set.

Offline Phase The analysis window is chosen in physical time so that all simulations are sampled from an equivalent dynamical regime, independent of the parameter value. For consistent visual comparison across parameters, however, all time-dependent data in this work are plotted in the non-dimensional time \tilde{t} . Snapshots of the u_x and u_y components of the velocity field \mathbf{U} are collected over the snapshot-index window $n \in [1000, 2000]$, corresponding to the physical-time interval $[10.0, 20.0]$ s for a time step of $\Delta t = 0.01$. This ensures that initial transients are excluded from the training set, as evidenced by the periodic lift-coefficient signals shown in Figures (A.1 and A.2). For each training parameter $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$ (here, Re), the resulting snapshot data form the state vector used in the reduced-order model. The dataset is partitioned into two segments: the snapshot indices $n \in [1000, 1500]$ are used for dimensionality reduction and training of the DMD operators, while the subsequent indices $n \in [1500, 2000]$ are reserved for forecasting and interpolation evaluation. This choice provides a clear separation between the learning and evaluation phases. The snapshot matrices \mathbf{X}^{μ_i} for each parameter μ_i are assembled and concatenated to form the global matrix \mathcal{X}_1 in Equation (2.20).

Figure 3.4: Cumulative energy of singular values for the snapshot matrix \mathcal{X}_1 .

Before we choose a rank r , a singular value decomposition (SVD) of the global snapshot matrix \mathcal{X}_1 is performed to determine an appropriate truncation rank so that maximum energy is retained. The cumulative energy (Figure (3.4)) retained by the first $r = 3$ singular values are sufficient to retain

99.99% of the system's energy with a residual content of 5.17×10^{-3} .

However, relying solely on this threshold risks discarding dynamically relevant structures and may make the regression stage sensitive to noise in the tail of the spectrum. To ensure robustness, we adopt a more conservative truncation to ensure robustness and avoid discrepancies in the regression stage, so a larger rank of $r = 30$ with a residual content of 1.1×10^{-5} is selected for the POD basis.

Online Phase In the online phase, we forecast the reduced states associated with the *training* parameters between the time instants $n \in [1500, 2000]$. Then using a Radial Basis Function (RBF) interpolator we predict the modal coefficients across the parameter space within the same time interval, enabling the evaluation of *unseen* parameter μ^* (here $Re^* = 170$).

3.3 Evaluation

Stability

We start by looking at the eigenvalues λ_j of the first few dominant modes for the *training* parameters in Figure (3.5). The eigenvalues form a cluster close to the unit circle, producing a ring-like structure that is characteristic of systems dominated by periodic or quasi-periodic behaviour. Since these eigenvalues are obtained from DMD applied to the velocity-field, the structure observed in laminar cylinder flow corresponds to the von Kármán vortex shedding, which represents a stable limit cycle. Figure (3.5) shows that several complex-conjugate pairs lie very close to $|\lambda| = 1$, indicating neutrally stable oscillatory modes associated with the saturated shedding dynamics. As the parameter Re increases, the imaginary parts of these pairs shift smoothly along the angular direction, reflecting the increase in shedding frequency with Re . This smooth progression across the parameter space is important because pDMD relies on the assumption that the underlying dynamics vary continuously with the parameter. Eigenvalues that fall slightly inside the unit circle correspond to decaying transient modes, which naturally dissipate as the flow settles onto the limit cycle. Overall, all eigenvalues remain inside or very close to the unit circle for all Reynolds numbers, suggesting that the DMD operators are stable and do not introduce any exponential growth.

Figure 3.5: Eigenvalue spectrum of DMD *training* parameters.

Accuracy

Now, we analyze the trained DMD models in the time and frequency domain by plotting the POD modal coefficients and their Fast Fourier transform (FFT) (Figure (3.6)). While the eigenvalues characterize the stability and oscillatory nature of the learned dynamics, the POD coefficients ($a_j(t) = \langle x(t), \psi_j \rangle$) provide a direct comparison between the true temporal evolution of the system and the one reconstructed by the DMD operator. For the training parameter μ_i (i.e., $Re = 160$) the first few dominant modal coefficients are shown in Figure (3.6(a)). The reconstructed modal coefficients show excellent agreement with the true POD coefficients across modes. The first POD mode ψ_1 corresponds to a slowly varying, low frequency component ($St \approx 0$). The subsequent modes form oscillatory pairs, corresponding to the dominant oscillatory structures of the flow. In particular, the leading pair (ψ_2 and ψ_3) represents the vortex-shedding dynamics, and their modal coefficients exhibit nearly perfect phase alignment and amplitude matching between the true data and the DMD reconstruction. This indicates that the learned DMD operator accurately captures the underlying behaviour associated with the von Kármán vortex street. Higher-order modes ($\psi_j > 3$), such as

mode ψ_5 , ψ_7 and ψ_9 typically correspond to the higher harmonics of the primary shedding modes and are weaker or more transient flow features. These are also reproduced with high fidelity and without artificial drift or spurious growth.

Figure 3.6: Training parameter $Re = 160$ POD modal coefficients and their corresponding Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

As the DMD model is trained directly on the POD modal coefficients $a_j(t)$, this modal structure (i.e., steady mode followed by oscillatory pairs) is inherited naturally from the POD basis. The resulting dynamics confirm that the trained DMD model is both stable and physically consistent in the time domain. Their FFT (Figure (3.6(b))) reveals that the trained DMD model captures the correct dominant frequencies and harmonic content of each mode. Across all modes, the DMD model reproduces the spectral peaks of the true data accurately. The primary shedding frequency appears at the correct Strouhal number, and its amplitude closely matches that of the true signal. Secondary peaks and harmonics are also well aligned, demonstrating that the DMD operator preserves not only the dominant oscillation but also the finer spectral structure of the flow dynamics.

This spectral agreement is particularly important, since the interpolation stage relies on the assumption that the frequency content of the modal coefficients $a_j(t)$ vary smoothly across the parameters μ_i . The accurate reproduction of both the time-domain trajectories and the frequency spectra at $Re = 160$ confirms that the trained DMD model provides a reliable basis for forecasting and interpolation.

Figure 3.7: Flow comparison of *training* parameter $Re = 160$.

The flow field comparison in Figure (3.7) provides a spatial validation of the trained DMD model. We directly contrast the reconstructed velocity magnitude with the true snapshots at several time instants $\tilde{t} = 224.0, 232.0, 240.0$, along with the absolute residual $Residual_{abs}$ as $|U_{\text{True}} - U_{\text{ParametricDMD}}|$. The true and ParametricDMD fields exhibit nearly identical flow structures, including the alternating shear layers and the downstream wake pattern characteristic of vortex shedding. The agreement persists across all shown time instants, and confirming that the DMD operator successfully reconstructs the dominant coherent structures in physical space. The residual fields remain small and spatially localized, primarily around regions of strong gradients such as the shear layers and near-wake vortices.

To compute the reconstruction error accumulated over the whole time window we define the relative L^2 reconstruction error ε_{rel} as,

$$\varepsilon_{\text{rel}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{True}}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{True}}\|_2} = \frac{\|x(t_n) - x(t_n)_{\text{True}}\|_2}{\|x(t_n)_{\text{True}}\|_2} \quad (3.1)$$

and the mean reconstruction error $\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{rel}}$ as,

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{rel}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_{\text{True}}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{True}}\|_2} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\|x(t_n) - x(t_n)_{\text{True}}\|_2}{\|x(t_n)_{\text{True}}\|_2} \quad (3.2)$$

Here, \mathbf{X} are the DMD reconstructed snapshots whereas \mathbf{X}_{True} represents the true snapshot ac-

quired from simulations. Figure (3.8) show that the mean relative error $\bar{\epsilon}_{\text{rel}}$ for the DMD training window is approximately 0.29% (Figure (3.8(a))) and when the learned DMD operator is used to propagate the dynamics forward in time, this error remains comparably low over the forecast window at 0.30% (Figure (3.8(b))) .

The negligible increase of only 0.01% between the training and forecast phases demonstrates that the DMD operator successfully extracts the underlying governing dynamics rather than merely memorizing the training snapshots. The oscillations observed in the error plots (Figures (3.8(a)) and (3.8(b))) correspond to the periodic vortex shedding. As the flow is periodic, the difference between two periodic signals is also periodic, even if the DMD reconstruction is extremely accurate. It produces a small oscillation in the error curve.

Figure 3.8: ParametricDMD reconstruction error for training and forecasting of *training* parameter $Re = 160$.

However, when we compare the interpolated prediction for an *unseen* parameter μ^* i.e., $Re^* = 170$, it reveals a fundamental breakdown in the model's ability to generalize beyond the *training* parameters. While this DMD approach achieves a high degree of fidelity at the *training* parameters in the training and forecast window with a mean error of only 0.3% at $Re = 160$, the interpolation at $Re^* = 170$ fails to provide a physically or mathematically consistent representation of the flow. The model doesn't accurately reconstruct the steady mode ψ_1 (Figure (3.9(a))).

For the oscillatory modes ψ_3 through ψ_9 in Figure (3.9(a)), the interpolated signals exhibit a "beating" phenomena, where the amplitude periodically inflates and contracts in a manner entirely absent from the true physics. This is a direct symptom of phase interference inherent to this interpolation pipeline, because the Radial Basis Function (RBF) operates by interpolating the values of the modal coefficients $a_j(t)$ at each discrete time step without knowledge of the underlying frequency shift, it performs a weighted summation of signals with disparate Strouhal numbers. This structural failure is further confirmed by the spectral analysis shown in Figure (3.9(b)), which reveals the emergence of "spectral splitting", where the true data exhibits a single, sharp frequency peak corresponding to the correct vortex shedding frequency for $Re^* = 170$, the interpolated model replaces this with a

dual-peak structure.

Figure 3.9: POD modal coefficients for the *Unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ (a) and Fast Fourier Transform along with neighbouring *training* parameters (b).

This indicates that the interpolation is blending two incompatible frequencies from the neighboring training anchors ($Re = 160$ and $Re = 180$) rather than finding the correct intermediate Strouhal number. In the FFT (Figure (3.9(b))), it can also be observed that the interpolated signal is a superposition of both anchors rather than a physically meaningful trajectory at $Re^* = 170$. As a result, the system's energy is distributed across two artificial spectral components, demonstrating that this PODI-based parametric DMD cannot transport frequency content smoothly across the parameter space.

The spatial consequences of these mathematical artifacts become strikingly evident when examining the flow field reconstruction in Figure (3.10). The comparison of the true velocity magnitude versus the interpolated flow field reveals a localized but severe accumulation of error, primarily concentrated within the wake region behind the cylinder. As observed in the flow field snapshots, the interpolated field displays distorted vortex structures at $\tilde{t} = 255.0$ that lack the sharp definition present in the high-fidelity simulation and almost completely reversed structures at $\tilde{t} = 272.0$. In the residual plots, this degradation is quantified where peak errors reach high values in the dynamic wake region. This breakdown in generalization is most clearly quantified by the evolution of the relative L^2 error shown in Figure (3.11). For this *unseen* $Re^* = 170$ parameter, the model yields a

substantial mean error of 28.47%, a stark contrast to the 0.3% error observed at the training anchors.

Figure 3.10: Flow comparison of *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

It can be seen from its evolution, that the reconstruction quality is highly unstable, with the L^2 error oscillating between near-zero values and peaks exceeding 60%. These error spikes correlate precisely with the "beating" cycles observed in the modal coefficients (Figure (3.9(a))), when the interpolated signals from the *training* neighbors drift into an anti-phase state, the resulting destructive interference causes a catastrophic collapse in the spatial reconstruction.

Figure 3.11: ParametricDMD reconstruction error for *unseen* parameter Re^*170 .

This comprehensive mismatch confirms that while the ParametricDMD class is effective at reproducing training data, its reliance on time-step-wise RBF interpolation renders it unable to capture the frequency glide and phase synchronization required to accurately predict the physics of unseen flow regimes.

Noise sensitivity

Figure 3.12: Added noise to the snapshots of each *training* parameter.

We now evaluate the robustness of the ParametricDMD framework under non-ideal conditions. A signal-scaled Gaussian noise is introduced into the training snapshots (Figure (3.12)). This perturbation which is governed by a custom injection function, modifies the snapshot matrices $\mathbf{X}^{(\mu_i)}$ per spatial point relative to a local scaling factor δ_x . For each training parameter μ_i , the noisy snapshots are generated as,

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{noisy}}^{(\mu_i)} = \mathbf{X}^{(\mu_i)} + \mathcal{N}(0, 1) \delta_x \eta \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ denotes a standard normal Gaussian random variable, δ_x is the noise-scaling coefficient, and η is the prescribed noise percentage. Three noise intensities are considered in this study, corresponding to $\eta \in \{10\%, 20\%, 40\%\}$. We begin the analysis by examining the impact of noise on the DMD eigenvalues. In the noise-free case in Figure (3.5), the eigenvalues λ_j of the dominant modes φ_j characterizing the periodic vortex shedding lie exactly on the unit circle ($|\lambda| = 1$) and on the negative $\Re(\lambda)$. However, as the noise level increases from 10% to 40%, a distinct clustering and inward migration is observed through Appendix Figures (A.3), (A.4) and (A.5). In addition to this inward movement, the dominant conjugate pair also undergoes a noticeable phase shift. While the noise-free eigenvalues appear on the negative $\Re(\lambda)$ of the complex plane, the introduction of noise

rotates this pair toward the positive $\Re(\lambda)$, even though the underlying oscillation frequency remains unchanged. Instead of merely scattering, the eigenvalues exhibit a systematic bias toward the interior of the unit circle ($|\lambda| < 1$), and the weaker higher-index modes collapse toward the center, forming the characteristic noise-induced clustering.

Figure 3.13: ParametricDMD reconstruction error of DMD training parameter $Re = 160$ after adding noise.

This "eigenvalue shrinkage" introduces artificial numerical damping, effectively biasing the growth rates of the captured dynamic modes and preventing the model from sustaining true physical dynamics. Despite the observed spectral bias toward $\lambda = 0$, the model initially demonstrates resilience during the reconstruction of training data. Suggesting that the POD-based dimensionality reduction acts as a low-pass filter. It de-noises snapshots before the DMD operator is fitted, this helps preserve the dominant spatial structures. For $Re = 160$, the mean L^2 reconstruction error remains remarkably low, even as noise increases: 0.48% at 10% noise, 0.92% at 20% noise, and 1.80% at 40% noise (Figure (3.13)).

However, a gradual degradation emerges during the forecasting phase (Figure (3.16)). The model relies on the repeated application of the biased, "shrunken" eigenvalues, so small damping errors accumulate over the temporal horizon. This leads to a mild but steady increase in the relative L^2 error for the training parameters within the forecast window. At 10% noise, the forecast error rises to a mean of 1.92%. At 20% noise, the error increases to 3.81% as the eigenvalue cluster shifts further inward. At 40% noise, the mean error reaches 6.30%, reflecting a cumulative drift in which the predicted state slowly deviates from the true trajectory over time.

Figure 3.14: ParametricDMD forecasting error for *training* parameter $Re = 160$ after adding noise.

This temporal instability confirms that while the `ParametricDMD` class is effective at spatial denoising, its predictive stability is highly sensitive to noise. The breakdown in generalization is most visible when examining the modal dynamics of the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ under noise. As shown in Figure (3.15(a)), the introduction of noise does not merely add stochastic fluctuations, it causes a fundamental loss of energy in the reconstructed signal.

For modes ψ_5 and ψ_7 in Figure (3.15(a)), the signal is almost entirely extinguished at 40% noise, and somehow over-amplified for all noise levels for mode ψ_9 . This correlates with the inward clustering of eigenvalues previously identified, which introduces excessive numerical damping into the system. The "beating" phenomenon observed in the noise-free case (Figure (3.9)) persists across all noise levels, indicating that the phase interference introduced by the RBF interpolator is not eliminated by noise injection but instead becomes increasingly obscured as the signal-to-noise ratio decreases. The frequency-domain analysis in Figure (3.15(b)) provides the final confirmation of the model's breakdown. The spectral splitting observed previously (where energy is erroneously partitioned into two phantom peaks) is now accompanied by significant spectral broadening. As the noise level increases, the FFT reveals a collapse in peak intensity. At 40% noise, the spectral peaks for modes ψ_5 and ψ_7 effectively disappear into the noise floor. This suggests that the `ParametricDMD` model fails to preserve the coherent periodic structure of the vortex street when operating outside the *training* set \mathcal{P} in noisy environments, as the energy of the dynamical system is dissipated across a wider frequency band rather than localized at the correct Strouhal number.

Figure 3.15: *Unseen* parameter ($Re^* = 170$) POD modal coefficients and their corresponding Fast Fourier Transform across noise levels.

A critical observation is the paradoxical relationship between noise levels and reconstruction accuracy for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$. As shown in Figure (3.16), the mean relative L^2 error for the interpolated case actually decreases as the noise increases, dropping from 28.47% at 10% to 26.90% at 40% noise. This however, is not an indicator of improved model performance, rather a consequence of the "eigenvalue shrinkage" previously identified. As observed in the noise-free case in Figure (3.9(a)) that the RBF interpolator creates significant "beating" cycles due to the phase interference of mismatched frequencies from the *training* anchors. This suggests that these interference events lead to large, periodic error spikes that drive up the mean L^2 error value in the noise-free model.

So, for 40% noise, the artificial numerical damping (induced by eigenvalues migrating to $|\lambda| < 1$) forces the oscillatory modal coefficients to decay rapidly. This effectively suppresses the amplitude of these signals and the noise prevents the high amplitude destructive interference that causes the massive 60% error peaks. In short, the error is lower because the model has become dynamically "inert" in a way that it predicts a decaying signal that stays closer to the mean flow than a large, incorrectly-phased oscillation.

Figure 3.16: ParametricDMD interpolation error for *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ after adding noise.

The evaluation of `ParametricDMD` reveals that the model is highly accurate for the *training* parameters μ_i and robust to spatial noise due to POD filtering. However, for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ it lacks the structural mechanism to handle frequency shifts across the parameter space. The reliance on time-step-wise RBF interpolation of POD coefficients leads to:

1. **Spectral Splitting:** the model blends neighbouring Strouhal frequencies instead of transporting them smoothly.
2. **Temporal Beating:** destructive phase interference between mismatched oscillatory components.
3. **Stability-Accuracy Trade-off:** noise-induced damping suppresses dynamics while artificially lowering the mean error.

Taken together, these effects demonstrate that this implementation is fundamentally constrained by its interpolation strategy. Since the algorithm interpolates POD modal coefficients independently at each time instant, rather than interpolating the underlying Koopman operators or their eigenvalues, it is unable to capture the continuous evolution of frequency, phase, or modal energy across parameters μ_i (i.e., Reynolds numbers). While the method performs exceptionally well at the *training* parameter (i.e., where no interpolation is required), it fails to generalize to *unseen* parameters μ^* where the dynamical spectrum shifts with μ_i . The resulting spectral artifacts, phase inconsistencies, and noise-driven damping are therefore not incidental but structural limitations of the approach.

4 Development of improved pDMD algorithm

The previous chapter (3) presented the results obtained using the `ParametricDMD` and revealed several systematic limitations. Most notably, the accuracy of the reconstructed trajectories deteriorated for *unseen* parameter μ^* values, exhibiting significant phase drift, amplitude mismatch, and distortions in the dominant spectral content.

These issues arise from the fact that the `ParametricDMD` workflow interpolates POD modal coefficients independently at each discrete time step. By performing a weighted summation of temporal signals from neighboring training anchors, the Radial Basis Function (RBF) interpolator ignores the underlying shift in the system's characteristic frequencies i.e., the Strouhal numbers (St). Consequently, for oscillatory flows, this approach results in destructive phase interference and "spectral splitting", where the model fails to smoothly transport the frequency peak and instead blends incompatible harmonics.

These observations motivate the development of an enhanced pDMD formulation that reduces error accumulation and preserves the intrinsic spectral structure of the dynamics across parameter space. In this chapter, we introduce an improved partitioned pDMD algorithm that bypasses POD-based coefficient interpolation and instead performs Lagrange point-wise interpolation directly on the spectral objects extracted from the partitioned DMD operators, namely the eigenvalues λ , the modes ϕ , and the initial condition x_0 . This mode-realigned pointwise interpolation (MRPWI) follows the algorithmic framework established in the original MRPWI formulation [10], in which the DMD modes and continuous-time eigenvalues are first spectrally aligned and then interpolated across parameters using Lagrange polynomials. Our work adopts this existing methodology and extends it in one respect that while the original formulation reconstructs the evolution using the true initial condition at the target parameter, our adaptation interpolates x_0 alongside the spectral quantities to maintain complete parametric consistency within the reduced model.

4.1 Design principles

The improved algorithm employs `FlowTorch` DMD implementation [47], where independent DMD models are trained for each parameter configuration $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$ (Figure (4.1)). We bypass the POD reduction step entirely and extract spectral information directly from the partitioned DMD operators \tilde{A}^{μ_i} .

For each parameter μ_i , the eigendecomposition of \tilde{A}^{μ_i} in Equation (2.13) yields modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ that are parameter-dependent, these modes encode the spatial structures and eigenvalues $\lambda_j^{\mu_i}$ for their associated growth/decay with oscillation rates. Instead of using these discrete-time eigenvalues $\lambda_j^{\mu_i}$,

Figure 4.1: Schematic workflow for spectral data extraction for MRPWI, inspired by [3].

we use their continuous-time counterparts $s_j^{\mu_i}$ to ensure the correct interpolation of both magnitude and phase of the complex-valued eigenvalues which is obtained as $s_j^{\mu_i} = \frac{\ln \lambda_j^{\mu_i}}{\Delta t}$ (where the real part of $s_j^{\mu_i}$ represents exponential growth or decay, while the imaginary part corresponds to the oscillation frequency [35]). As continuous-time eigenvalues separate these two effects explicitly, they are more suitable for interpolation across parameters μ_i .

4.2 Consistency and phase realignment of the DMD spectrum

Following the methodology in [10] we preprocess these quantities to make them more robust for interpolation. First, we rank the modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ and their associated eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu_i}$, because unlike POD whose modes are ordered by decreasing singular value, DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ have no intrinsic ordering. The modes may appear in any order, and this order may vary arbitrarily across parameters. Since there is no ordering of modes based on energy, a ranking criterion is required to identify the dynamically dominant structures. We rank the modes based on their integral contribution I_j [24] [47],

$$I_j^{\mu_i} = \|\phi_j^{\mu_i}\|_2^2 \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |b_j^{\mu_i} (\lambda_j^{\mu_i})^n|, \quad j = 1, \dots, r. \quad (4.1)$$

where $\|\phi_j^{\mu_i}\|_2^2$ denotes the squared Euclidean norm of the j -th DMD mode, and $|b_j^{\mu_i} (\lambda_j^{\mu_i})^n|$ represents the magnitude of the corresponding time-dependent modal coefficient. Here, integration is replaced by a summation since the snapshot time interval Δt is fixed. This contribution measures how strongly a mode $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ is expressed in both the spatial and temporal domains. The term $\|\phi_j^{\mu_i}\|_2^2$ represents the pointwise magnitude, ensuring that spatially significant structures are prioritized. The summation term captures the temporal activity so that modes that are persistent ($|\lambda_j^{\mu_i}| \approx 1$) or growing ($|\lambda_j^{\mu_i}| > 1$) result in large $I_j^{\mu_i}$ values. Conversely, numerically spurious or highly localized modes, which typically decay rapidly, contribute very little to the total sum and are assigned a lower rank.

Second, for real-valued flow data, the DMD operator is real and therefore its eigenvalues appear either as real numbers or as complex conjugate pairs $\lambda_j^{\mu_i}$. In continuous time, these correspond to conjugate pairs of growth/decay rates and oscillation frequencies $s_j^{\mu_i} = \rho_j^{\mu_i} \pm i\omega_j^{\mu_i}$. Each pair $(s_j^{\mu_i}, \overline{s_j^{\mu_i}})$ represents an oscillatory mode $(\phi_j^{\mu_i}, \overline{\phi_j^{\mu_i}})$ with identical spatial structure but a phase shift, which is a standard property of DMD applied to real-valued systems [34]. However, the order in which these conjugate modes appear is arbitrary and may vary across parameter values μ_i . To enforce a consistent pairing of eigenvalues and modes, we identify the conjugate partner $s_c^{\mu_i} = \overline{s_j^{\mu_i}}$ and reorder each pair so that the eigenvalue with positive imaginary part is placed first.

$$\Im(s_j^{\mu_i}) \geq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, p \quad (4.2)$$

Third, even after sorting and pairing, each complex DMD mode is still ambiguous up to a global phase factor,

$$\phi_j^{\mu_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_j^{\mu_i} e^{i\vartheta}. \quad (4.3)$$

Consequently, each mode $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ and its phase-shifted counterpart $\phi_j^{\mu_i} e^{i\vartheta}$ represents a spatial structure that is physically similar but mathematically rotated in the complex plane. This spatial phase represents the local oscillatory state of the flow field. The DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ being the eigenvectors (Equation (2.13)) of the reduced operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{\mu_i}$, possess a global phase ambiguity. This phase ϑ ambiguity is not physically invariant across the parameters μ_i . As DMD is performed independently for each μ_i , there is a global phase shift among modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ that does not account for the spatial continuity of the flow structures. This results in a 'phase jitter' across the parameter manifold, where physically similar structures appear mathematically rotated in the complex plane. If these modes are interpolated directly, the lack of phase coherence leads to destructive interference, producing physically meaningless results. Therefore, a realignment procedure is required to map the modes into a phase-coherent reference frame, ensuring that interpolation acts upon the true physical evolution of the coherent structures.

Therefore, we start by selecting a set of reference modes $\Phi^{\mu_{\text{ref}}}$ among *training* parameter μ_i which is closest to the *unseen* parameter μ^* . This selected mode set serves as the stationary phase target to which the neighbouring mode sets $\{\Phi^{\mu_i}\}_{i=2}^p$ are then aligned by column-wise rotation to this reference. To measure the angular shift between these complex vectors the idea of pseudo-angle φ is utilized. Following [22, 23, 33], the pseudo-angle among two complex vectors w and z is defined as,

$$e^{i\varphi(\phi_w, \phi_z)} = \frac{\langle \phi_w, \phi_z \rangle}{\|\phi_w\| \|\phi_z\|} \quad (4.4)$$

where $\langle \phi_w, \phi_z \rangle = \overline{\phi_w}^T \phi_z$ is the complex inner product. The specific pseudo-angle φ_{wz} can be calculated using the complex logarithm $\varphi = -i \ln e^{i\varphi}$, ensuring the value φ remains within the principal interval $[-\pi, \pi]$.

Building upon this idea, after selecting reference mode set $\Phi^{\mu_{\text{ref}}}$, each neighbouring parameter $\{\Phi^{\mu_i}\}_{i=2}^p$ is rotated to match the reference phase orientation. The realignment transformation is given by

$$\phi_j^{\mu_i} \rightarrow \phi_j^{\mu_i} e^{-i\varphi_j^{\mu_i}}, \quad i = 2, \dots, p; j = 1, \dots, r \quad (4.5)$$

where $\varphi_j^{\mu_i}$ is the pseudo-angle $\varphi(\phi_j^{\mu_{\text{ref}}}, \phi_j^{\mu_i})$ between the modes of reference $\phi_j^{\mu_{\text{ref}}}$ and the modes of neighbours $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ in the parameter space \mathcal{P} .

Figure 4.2: Schematic workflow for mode-realigned pointwise interpolation (MRPWI).

4.3 Implementation

Figure (4.2) shows the workflow of the improved pDMD algorithm. After enforcing consistent ordering, conjugate pairing, and phase realignment of the DMD spectrum across all training parameters $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$, we construct a local interpolation stencil around a previously *unseen* target parameter μ^* . Given the global parameter set $\mathcal{P} = \{\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_p\}$ we define, the proximity based stencil set \mathcal{S} for a chosen stencil size N_p ,

$$\mathcal{S}_{N_p} = \{\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_p\} \subset \mathcal{P}, \quad |\mu_{\text{ref}} - \mu^*| \text{ minimal} \quad (4.6)$$

where the number of selected parameters in the stencil, N_p . We create the stencil by sorting all training parameters according to their distance from the *unseen* parameter μ^* and selecting the N_p closest values (with N_p enforced to be even). Once this stencil is selected, we employ one-dimensional Lagrange interpolation across the parameter space \mathcal{P} . We interpolate the DMD modes Φ^{μ_i} , the continuous-time eigenvalues S^{μ_i} , and the initial condition $x_0^{\mu_i}$ for the *unseen* parameter μ^* using point-wise Lagrange interpolation over the selected stencil, in contrast to the work from which this method has been adapted [10]. They interpolate only the spectral objects and use the true initial condition, whereas we also interpolate $x_0^{\mu_i}$ to make the method fully parametric.

$$\mathcal{I}_{\mu^*} \begin{cases} \Phi^{\mu^*} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \ell_i(\mu^*) \Phi^{\mu_i} \\ S^{\mu^*} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \ell_i(\mu^*) S^{\mu_i} \\ x_0^{\mu^*} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \ell_i(\mu^*) x_0^{\mu_i} \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

with $\ell_i(\mu^*)$ denoting the Lagrange interpolation weights associated with the parameter stencil. This resulting triplet $(\Phi^{(\mu^*)}, S^{(\mu^*)}, x_0^{(\mu^*)})$ defines the prediction model at the *unseen* parameter μ^* . The evolution of the predicted flow is reconstructed using Equation (2.15) as,

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \Phi^{\mu^*} \exp(S^{\mu^*} t), \Phi^{\mu^* \dagger} x_0^{\mu^*} \quad (4.8)$$

5 Validation and analysis

5.1 Case Study I: Laminar Cylinder Flow

To evaluate the improved parametric DMD model introduced in Section (4), we maintain the 2D cylinder flow configuration and numerical parameters identical to the baseline benchmark described in Section (3.1). By utilizing the same training set $\mathcal{P} = \{Re = 100, 110, \dots, 200\}$, snapshot intervals, and a POD truncation rank of $r = 30$, we ensure that differences in predictive performance arise solely from the improved interpolation strategy.

Specific to this model, the lift coefficient $C_L(t)$ is now included in the DMD state vector to provide a global scalar measure of the unsteady wake dynamics and enable direct verification of the predicted vortex shedding. Predictive performance is assessed at the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ using the MRPWI formulation. Interpolation is performed using proximity-based stencil sets $\mathcal{S}_{N_p} \subset \mathcal{P}$ with sizes $N_p = 2, 4, 6$, allowing us to quantify the improvement in local spectral reconstruction as additional neighboring parameters are incorporated.

Figure 5.1: Eigenvalue spectrum of DMD *training* parameters.

Stability

To assess the stability and spectral behaviour of the DMD operators at each *training* parameter $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$, the eigenvalues λ^{μ_i} serve as the fundamental “spectral clock” of the system. After ranking modes by their integral contribution (Equation (4.1)), the dominant eigenvalues in Figure (5.1) exhibit a consistent structure across all Reynolds numbers. In every case, the most energetic modes consist of a neutral real eigenvalue at $\lambda = 1$, corresponding to the mean flow, followed by a sequence of symmetric conjugate pairs lying on the unit circle. These pairs represent the hierarchy of neutrally stable oscillatory modes associated with the periodic vortex-shedding dynamics.

This behaviour is fully consistent with the physics of a limit-cycle wake. For all parameters μ_i considered, the flow has already transitioned to periodic vortex shedding, and the dominant oscillatory mode is therefore neutrally stable. Consequently, its discrete-time eigenvalues satisfy $|\lambda_j| = 1$, and the corresponding continuous-time growth rates σ_j vanish in the relation $\lambda_j = e^{(\sigma_j + i\omega_j)\Delta t}$. The DMD evolution operator \tilde{A} thus preserves the amplitude of the shedding mode over arbitrarily long horizons, reflecting the physical balance between energy extraction from the mean flow and viscous dissipation in the saturated wake. And due to the operators \tilde{A}^{μ_i} being constructed without a preceding POD projection, the raw eigenvalue ordering does not enforce conjugate pairing; however, once modes are ranked by their integral contribution, the expected spectral symmetry becomes evident. The smooth shift of the dominant conjugate pairs along the unit circle with increasing Re confirms that the shedding frequency varies monotonically across the parameter set \mathcal{P} .

Accuracy

Now, to quantify the predictive accuracy of the partitioned DMD manifold, we evaluate the reconstructed lift coefficient $C_L(t)$ and its frequency content over the training interval $n \in [1000, 1500]$. Since the DMD operators are constructed directly in the full state space, there is no orthogonal basis onto which the dynamics are projected. Which implies that we don’t have an orthogonal basis, and without an orthogonal basis the modal coefficients become basis-dependent and therefore lack physical invariance across parameters μ_i . Accuracy is thus assessed through physical observables, namely the reconstructed lift coefficient and its spectral content.

Figure (5.2(a)) shows the reconstructed $C_L(t)$ for each *training* Reynolds number $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$. The reconstructions exhibit near perfect overlap with the true signals, demonstrating that the model accurately reproduces the saturated amplitude and phase of the limit cycle. This agreement results from the unit-modulus eigenvalues in Figure (5.1) which are in the fluctuation subspace, that strictly enforce neutral growth rates and prevent the amplitude drift typically observed in standard DMD formulations.

Figure 5.2: Training parameter lift coefficients C_L and their corresponding Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

The corresponding mean removed FFT magnitude spectra in Figure (5.2(b)) further validate the spectral fidelity of the trained operators \tilde{A}^{μ_i} . For every Re , the DMD manifold recovers a dominant,

sharply defined peak at the fundamental Strouhal frequency. The precise alignment of this peak with the reference spectrum confirms that the phase angles $\theta_j = \arg(\lambda_j)$ of the dominant eigenvalues encode the correct shedding frequency which increases smoothly with parameter (Re) as expected for the laminar cylinder wake. The absence of phase lag, amplitude distortion, or spectral leakage indicates that the unitary evolution imposed on the fluctuation subspace preserves the energy-dominant coherent structures of the wake.

To further assess the robustness of the trained model, we examine the temporal evolution of the relative L^2 error for a representative *training* parameter, $Re = 160$. As shown in Figure (5.3(a)), the reconstruction error for the training phase remains exceptionally low, with a mean value of approximately 0.01%. This level of precision indicates that the partitioned manifold accurately captures the underlying Koopman-invariant subspace governing the limit-cycle dynamics.

Figure 5.3: Relative L^2 error for DMD *training* parameter $Re = 160$ within the training (a) and forecasting (b) window.

The predictive capability of the model is evaluated by extending the integration into the forecasting window in the interval $[1500, 2000]$, beyond the temporal range used for training. For $Re = 160$ in Figure (5.3(b)), the relative L^2 error in the forecast regime remains stable and matches the training error at approximately 0.01%, exhibiting no significant growth or divergence. This temporal stability is a direct consequence of the unit-modulus eigenvalues, which prevent the accumulation of numerical errors that typically degrade standard DMD extrapolations. The consistency between training and forecasting errors demonstrates that the partitioned manifold successfully identifies a dynamically invariant subspace, providing a robust foundation for parametric interpolation.

5.1.1 Consistency and phase realignment

With the behavior of the trained operators $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{\mu_i}$ established, we now turn to how the MRPWI framework transports the spectral quantities extracted from the DMD decompositions toward the *unseen* parameter μ^* .

Figure 5.4: Distribution of modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ for a *training* parameter $Re = 160$.

As outlined in Section (4.2), successful interpolation of DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ requires that they be consistently ranked, paired, and phase-aligned across all *training* parameters. We therefore begin by examining the sorted modes on the *training* manifold, verifying that the ranking criterion adapted from [24,47] produces a coherent and dynamically meaningful ordering that can serve as a reliable basis for interpolation.

The ranked modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ exhibit a uniform and repeatable distribution across all training Reynolds numbers, confirming that the criterion I_j indeed produces a coherent and dynamically meaningful ordering suitable for interpolation. This behavior contrasts with standard DMD, where the extracted modes have no inherent physical or energetic ordering: the algorithm simply returns eigenvectors of the companion matrix in an arbitrary sequence [34], and even the exact DMD formulation does not tie modal ordering to frequency, growth rate, or energy [43]. By enforcing a consistent ranking, each modal index j corresponds to a physically meaningful contribution at every Re , most notably the fundamental shedding mode and its higher harmonics. This effect is clearly visible in Figure (5.4), where the first five ranked modes display stable and interpretable spatial patterns for a *training* parameter $Re = 160$.

In the unranked case (right), the spatial fields are mis-ordered where the mean flow ϕ_0 and the fundamental shedding mode ϕ_1 are assigned to inconsistent indices ϕ_2 and ϕ_0 respectively. Higher harmonics appear out of sequence as well. Once the modes are ranked (left), the physical hierarchy is restored, the mean flow mode appears as ϕ_1 followed by a clear progression of the primary shedding mode and its downstream harmonics. The spatial coherence of the ranked modes confirms that the procedure correctly identifies and orders the dominant flow structures. Enforcing this consistent ordering, we guarantee that the j -th mode at $Re = 100$ represents the same physical phenomenon as the j -th mode at $Re = 200$. This topological alignment is essential for the MR-PWI framework, as it prevents the interpolation of mismatched physical features and enables the smooth transport of vortex-shedding dynamics across the parameter space.

Building on this alignment, the efficacy of the phase-realignment procedure is assessed by examining the evolution of the pseudo-angle φ across the training parameters. Here, the pseudo-angle φ is evaluated at a fixed spatial location for each mode, specifically the point where the corresponding reference mode attains its maximum magnitude. As shown in Figure (5.5), the unaligned modes (black) exhibit large, irregular fluctuations in their phase values. This pronounced “phase jitter” arises from the global phase ambiguity $e^{i\theta}$ inherent to independent DMD solves [34]. As a result, every unaligned mode $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ shows phase variations approaching almost 10 radians across the Reynolds number range, which would lead to destructive interference during interpolation.

So, after applying the realignment transformation by rotating the modes as given in Equation (4.5), the aligned modes (red) collapse onto smooth, nearly stationary trajectories (Figure (5.5)). For the mean mode $\phi_1^{\mu_i}$, the phase is anchored at zero, while the oscillatory modes $\phi_2^{\mu_i} - \phi_3^{\mu_i}$ and $\phi_4^{\mu_i} - \phi_5^{\mu_i}$ exhibit consistent, physically meaningful phase evolution with increasing Re . This transformation maps the spectral data into a phase coherent reference frame, ensuring that the Lagrange interpolation operates on topologically aligned states.

Figure 5.5: Evolution of the phase φ (rad) across the *training* parameters μ_i (Re).

5.1.2 Mode-Realigned Pointwise Interpolation

Modes and Eigenvalues

Figure (5.6) presents the continuous-time DMD eigenvalues s_j in the complex plane of 2-point stencil N_p ($Re \in [160, 180]$) for Lagrange point-wise interpolation. The *training* parameters $Re = 160$ and $Re = 180$, and the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ shown both before and after applying the mode-ranking and realignment procedures. Each column displays the eigenvalues associated with a single Reynolds number, with the horizontal axis representing $\Re(s)$ and the vertical axis representing $\Im(s)$.

Figure 5.6: Interpolated eigenvalues for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ and neighbouring *training* parameters for $N_p = 2$.

The black labels denote the raw modal indices obtained directly from standard DMD, while the red labels indicate the ranked indices after enforcing a consistent ordering across parameters. The impact and importance of this mode ranking and realignment on the eigenvalues s_j interpolation becomes clear. As expected for periodic vortex shedding, the eigenvalues $s_j^{H_i}$ at the *training* param-

eters μ_i form complex conjugate pairs (red) that lie approximately along the imaginary axis [30, 34], with the eigenvalue at the origin corresponding to the mean flow [30, 36] (with $\Re(s_0) \approx 0$ and $\Im(s_0) \approx 0$) that have no exponential growth/decay and oscillation behaviour. This spectral structure reflects the purely oscillatory nature of the cylinder wake and provides a physically meaningful reference against which interpolation can be assessed.

In the raw, unaligned interpolation (black), the eigenvalues at $Re^* = 170$ exhibit clear inconsistencies, several modes are mis-paired, the conjugate symmetry is not preserved, and the imaginary parts do not follow the smooth progression observed between $Re = 160$ and $Re = 180$. As standard DMD does not impose any intrinsic ordering on modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ or eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu_i}$ [34, 43], the interpolation is performed between mismatched spectral components. As a result, the interpolated eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu^*}$ deviate from the physical branches of the spectrum and fail to reproduce the expected modal structure. This behavior mirrors the mis-ordering observed earlier in the unranked modes and highlights the incompatibility of raw DMD spectra for parametric interpolation.

In contrast, the ranked and phase-aligned interpolation (red) produces eigenvalues $\phi_j^{\mu^*}$ at $Re^* = 170$ that lie smoothly between their counterparts at $Re = 160$ and $Re = 180$. Each ranked index traces a single continuous spectral branch across the parameter space, and the conjugate-pair structure is preserved throughout. The smooth variation of $\Im(s)$ confirms that the combination of vortex shedding mode ranking [24] and phase realignment eliminates the artificial permutations and phase rotations that arise from independent DMD computations [34]. Consequently, the interpolated eigenvalues accurately reflect the underlying dynamics and remain consistent with the spectra obtained directly from DMD at the neighboring Reynolds numbers.

This demonstrates that mode ranking and realignment is essential for constructing a topologically coherent spectral manifold. Only after enforcing this consistency do the DMD eigenvalues s_j vary smoothly with the parameters μ_i , enabling reliable interpolation of both modes ϕ_j and eigenvalues s_j within the MRPWI framework.

To further assess the quality of the interpolated prediction, Figure (5.7) compares the real and imaginary components of the interpolated eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu^*}$ at the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ against the true DMD spectrum. Across all stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$), the dominant eigenvalues exhibit excellent agreement with the ground truth. In the real-part plot (above), the leading oscillatory modes form nearly flat branches, and the interpolated values lie directly on top of the true $\Re(s_j^{\mu^{true}})$ curve. This reflects the fact that each conjugate pair shares the same real part, and the interpolation preserves this pairing for all N_p . The conjugate-pair structure is apparent in the imaginary-part plot where each oscillatory pair appears as two symmetric values of opposite sign, with $\Im(s_j^{\mu^{true}})$ and $-\Im(s_j^{\mu^{true}})$ forming smooth, continuous branches across the mode index. The interpolated curves reproduce this symmetry for all stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$), demonstrating that the MRPWI alignment maintains both the correct ordering and the correct pairing of the oscillatory modes. This behaviour

confirms that, once the spectral manifold is coherently aligned, even a minimal two-point stencil is sufficient to recover the physically relevant oscillatory dynamics. Small deviations arise only in the high-index portion of the spectrum, where the eigenvalues have small magnitude and are more sensitive to numerical noise.

Figure 5.7: Real and imaginary parts of the interpolated eigenvalues for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ across all stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$).

These discrepancies increase mildly with stencil size, reflecting the reduced smoothness of the spectral tail and the inherent instability of the weak modes. Small deviations arise only in the high-index portion of the spectrum, where the eigenvalues have small magnitude and are more sensitive to

numerical noise. Nevertheless, the overall branch topology remains intact for all N_p , and the interpolated eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu*}$ do not exhibit the mis-pairing or discontinuities characteristic of the unranked interpolation. This reinforces that the MRPWI framework provides a robust and physically consistent means of interpolating the dynamically coherent portion of the DMD spectrum.

Figure 5.8: Real component of true DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu \text{true}}$ and the interpolated modes $\phi_j^{\mu*}$ for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

A similar level of consistency is observed in the interpolated modes in Figure (5.8). The performance of the interpolation procedure is evaluated using a minimal stencil of $N_p = 2$ training anchors ($Re \in \{160, 180\}$) to predict the dynamics at the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$. Since the oscillatory DMD modes appear in conjugate pairs, we plot the top five modes $j = 1, 3, 5, \dots$ (excluding the mean mode). The predicted modes $\phi_j^{\mu^*}$ preserve the essential physics of the cylinder wake with high accuracy.

The primary shedding mode $\phi_1^{\mu^*}$ with their downstream harmonics $\phi_3^{\mu^*}$ and $\phi_5^{\mu^*}$ capture the antisymmetric vortex patterns and the characteristic spatial decay of the wake. This close spatial correspondence, including the resolution of higher harmonics in the far field, confirms that the interpolation maintains the structure of the modal subspace without the ghosting or blurring that appears in non-aligned interpolation methods. The sharpness of the predicted spatial features indicates that the modal energy and spatial distribution are transported smoothly along the parameter manifold, even when the target Re^* lies between sparse training points.

The corresponding interpolated modal phases in Figure (5.9) further validate the robustness of the realignment procedure. The phase field $\varphi_j = \arg(\phi_j)$ describes the local timing of the oscillation associated with each complex DMD mode, indicating which regions of the flow lead or lag in the periodic vortex shedding cycle. Comparing the interpolated and true phase fields therefore provides a direct test of whether the interpolation preserves the oscillatory structure of the mode.

For each mode, the predicted phase reproduces the downstream phase progression and the expected symmetric or antisymmetric behaviour about the wake center-line. The dominant modes show almost perfect agreement with the ground truth, reflecting the strong coherence of the dominant limit-cycle dynamics. Higher order modes ($j \geq 5$) exhibit small deviations in regions with steep phase gradients, but their overall topological structure remains intact. This demonstrates that the MRPWI framework preserves the full complex-valued modal structure. In addition to the amplitude it also captures the spatial distribution of phase φ_j . Suggesting that maintaining the correct local oscillatory state and relative phase offsets across the flow field, the reconstructed time series retains the physically correct timing relationships between spatial regions. Consequently, once the spectral manifold is coherently aligned, even a minimal training set (i.e., $N_p = 2$) is sufficient to interpolate both the real-valued spatial structures and the complex phase information in a physically consistent manner. While the dominant modes interpolate cleanly in both amplitude and phase, the behaviour of the higher index modes naturally reflects their reduced coherence. The behaviour of these weak modes carries directly over to their interpolation accuracy. Since the tail of the DMD spectrum is dominated by low-energy, rapidly oscillatory structures, the corresponding interpolated modes are inherently more sensitive to perturbations and exhibit reduced parametric smoothness.

Figure 5.9: Phase of true DMD modes $\arg(\phi_j^{\mu^* \text{true}})$ and the interpolated modes $\arg(\phi_j^{\mu^*})$ for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

This is reflected clearly in the interpolation error calculated using the Equations (5.1) at $Re^* = 170$ (Figure (5.10(a))).

$$\varepsilon_{\text{mode}}(j) = \frac{\|\phi_j^{\mu^*} - \phi_j^{\mu^{\text{true}}}\|_2}{\|\phi_j^{\mu^{\text{true}}}\|_2}, \quad \varepsilon_{\text{eig}}(j) = \frac{|s_j^{\mu^*} - s_j^{\mu^{\text{true}}}|}{|s_j^{\mu^{\text{true}}}|} \quad (5.1)$$

The relative error remains small and nearly flat across the dynamically relevant modes, begins to increase once the mode index exceeds $j \approx 20$, and then exhibits a sharp jump in the final few modes. These high index modes contribute little to the physical dynamics [34, 43], so the rapid growth in error for $j \gtrsim 25$ is fully consistent with their limited coherence and reduced smoothness. Importantly, this behaviour does not affect the coherent portion of the modal basis.

Figure 5.10: Interpolation error for modes (a) and eigenvalues (b) for *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

A similar trend appears in the eigenvalue interpolation (Figure (5.10(b))). The dominant eigenvalues which are associated with the limit-cycle oscillation are recovered with high accuracy for all stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$), while the small-magnitude eigenvalues in the spectral tail show larger deviations. These eigenvalues are highly sensitive to numerical noise and exhibit limited smoothness across parameters μ_i (i.e., Reynolds number), so their interpolation error is expected to increase with mode index j . Importantly, the errors remain confined to the weak end of the spectrum, and the dynamically relevant eigenvalues interpolate reliably.

This behavior persists when the interpolation procedure is repeated for the other parameters μ_i within the training set \mathcal{P} . By treating each $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$ in turn as an *unseen* parameter using a leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) approach, the Appendix Figures (A.6 and A.7) and their corresponding Tables (A.1 and A.2) suggests a similar behaviour for all parameters. Across all test parameters $\mu_i \in \mathcal{P}$, the interpolation error remains uniformly small for the dominant portion of the spectrum. For the first 5–20 modes, the modal errors remain within $\mathcal{O}(10^{-3})$ – $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ and the eigenvalue errors within $\mathcal{O}(10^{-2})$ – $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$, with only mild dependence on the stencil size. Beyond approximately $j \approx 20$, the errors increase sharply. For example, at $Re = 100$ the mode error grows from $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ (20 modes) to $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ – $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$ (25 modes), and reaches $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$ at 30 modes, while the eigenvalue error escalates from $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ to $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$ and finally $\mathcal{O}(10^1)$. Similar behaviour appears at all other parameters,

including interior values such as $Re = 130$ and $Re = 150$, where the first 20 modes remain accurate but the tail modes deteriorate rapidly. This pattern is consistent across all stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$), indicating that the weak, low-energy modes lack parametric smoothness and are highly sensitive to perturbations. The collective LOOCV results therefore provide sort of a guideline for selecting the reconstruction rank of approximately $r \approx 20$ that captures the dynamically coherent portion of the spectrum, while including higher-index modes doesn't contribute as much towards the reconstruction and in turn they degrade both modal and eigenvalue interpolation accuracy.

Initial condition (x_0)

Building on the modal-level analysis, we now analyse the interpolation of the initial condition $x_0^{\mu^*}$. For the *unseen* case $Re^* = 170$ (Figure (5.11(a))), the interpolated fields reproduce the expected large-scale vortex-shedding structures across stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$), giving an initial impression that $x_0^{\mu^*}$ vary smoothly enough with the parameter to support polynomial interpolation. However, once the Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation is evaluated, this impression does not hold. As can be seen in the Appendix Figure (A.8) and Table (A.3), the relative L^2 error fluctuates strongly across the parameter set \mathcal{P} , with no monotonic or predictable trend. Interior parameters such as $Re = 130$ exhibit errors of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$, whereas parameters near the edges of the set reach $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$ (e.g. $Re = 200$ for $N_p = 6$). These variations occur despite all cases belonging to the laminar vortex-shedding regime. Small phase offsets between limit-cycle snapshots at adjacent Reynolds numbers already introduce discrepancies that polynomial interpolation cannot compensate for, revealing that $x_0^{\mu^*}$ does not possess the parametric smoothness required for reliable Lagrange-based reconstruction.

To determine whether this behaviour is specific to the laminar regime or reflects a more fundamental limitation of the interpolation strategy, the analysis extends to the higher Reynolds subset $\mathcal{R} = \{400, 410, \dots, 500\}$. In this range, the cylinder wake enters the laminar-turbulent transitional regime, where the vortex-shedding dynamics change rapidly with Reynolds number. The topology of the instantaneous flow field no longer evolves smoothly (i.e., the orientation of the shedding pattern), the curvature of the shear layers, and the location of the vortex roll-up all shift in ways that are incompatible with a low-order parametric manifold.

As a result, the interpolated $x_0^{\mu^*}$ in the test set \mathcal{R} at $Re^* = 470$ (Figure (5.11(b))) does not simply degrade; it exhibits a qualitatively different wake structure. Even when more stencil points are used, the interpolated reconstruction cannot recover the correct shape, because all available initial condition $x_0^{\mu_i}$ snapshots across parameters correspond to flow fields with different shedding geometry. This mismatch is also clearly visible in the high-Reynolds training set \mathcal{R} (Appendix Figure (A.9)), where the instantaneous flow fields themselves vary in orientation, shear-layer curvature, and vortex roll-up location, preventing any low-order polynomial from capturing a coherent parametric

trend.

Figure 5.11: Interpolated initial condition x_0 comparison between laminar and transition regime for the *unseen* parameters $Re^* = 170$ and $Re^* = 470$, respectively.

The relative L^2 errors in Appendix Table (A.4) reflect this behaviour that even using a stencil $N_p = 2$ yields errors of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ – $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$, while higher-order interpolation amplifies the mismatch dramatically, reaching $\mathcal{O}(10^1)$ for $N_p = 6$ at the upper end of the parameter range. These large and highly variable errors confirm that the instantaneous flow fields in this transitional regime do not vary with the smoothness required for polynomial interpolation. Consequently, the interpolated $\mathbf{x}_0^{\mu^*}$ fails to reproduce the physically correct oscillatory state of the target parameter μ^* and cannot be used as a reliable component in parametric DMD modelling. Across both laminar and transitional regimes, the initial condition \mathbf{x}_0 exhibits error magnitudes ranging from $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ to $\mathcal{O}(10^1)$, demonstrating that it does not lie on a smoothly varying parametric manifold and is therefore unsuitable for direct interpolation in parametric DMD.

These results suggest that, rather than attempting to interpolate the initial condition \mathbf{x}_0 directly, a more robust strategy is to decouple its role from the parametric dependence. As discussed in Section (2.2), the spatial modes ϕ_j encode the coherent structures of the flow, while the eigenvalues s_j encode their temporal dynamics. Our results show that both quantities vary smoothly with the parameter, whereas the phase of the initial condition \mathbf{x}_0 does not. However, as it primarily determines the amplitude and phase of the modal expansion and therefore does not carry parametric information, we can use a neighbour's \mathbf{x}_0 . Motivated by this observation, we construct parametric predictions by combining interpolated modes ϕ^{μ^*} and eigenvalues s^{μ^*} with a non-interpolated initial condition $\mathbf{x}_0^{\mu_c}$ taken from the closest available *training* parameter μ_i . Specifically, for a target *unseen* parameter μ^* we select the nearest neighbour $\mu_c \in \mathcal{P}$ and use the corresponding true $\mathbf{x}_0^{\mu_c}$ as the initial state in the DMD reconstruction for the *unseen* parameter μ^* . To ensure that this initial condition $\mathbf{x}_0^{\mu_c}$ is used consistently, we apply a phase-alignment step at the *unseen* parameter μ^* . It is obtained by cross-correlating the interpolated lift coefficient $C_L^{\mu^*}(t)$ with the true $C_L(t)$ and shifting the true trajectory by the resulting lag before evaluating the reconstruction. This provides a consistent and physically meaningful alignment while preserving the smooth parametric behaviour of the modes and eigenvalues and avoiding the ill-posed interpolation of the initial condition on a non-smooth parametric manifold.

To assess whether this nearest-neighbour initial-condition strategy preserves the temporal dynamics for the *unseen* parameter, we first examine the lift coefficient C_L spectra for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$. Figure (5.12) presents a comparison between the true and predicted lift coefficient spectra on both linear and log scale. In the mean-removed spectrum (Figure (5.12)), both the true and predicted signals exhibit a dominant peak at $St \approx 0.25$, corresponding to the primary vortex-shedding frequency, and a secondary peak at $St \approx 0.5$ associated with the first harmonic which is visible on the log-scale spectrum in Figure (5.12(a)). Beyond the first harmonic at $St \approx 0.5$, the log-scale spectrum also reveals a sequence of low-amplitude peaks at higher Strouhal numbers. Although these peaks lie deep in the negative log-magnitude range, the predicted signal reproduces them with remarkable accuracy for every stencil size ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$) considered. The correct alignment

of these weak spectral features is significant in a way that such peaks arise from subtle higher-order modal interactions and fine-scale temporal structures that contribute only marginally to the total energy of the lift signal.

Figure 5.12: FFT of the True and interpolated lift coefficient C_L for the *unseen* parameter $Re = 170$.

Their accurate reconstruction indicates that the model does not merely capture the dominant shedding dynamics, but also preserves the delicate higher-frequency content embedded in the flow. Matching these low-amplitude peaks across all N_p confirms that the proposed approach retains the full oscillatory behaviour present in the true signal, even in regions where the spectral energy is several orders of magnitude smaller than the primary shedding peak. Crucially, this precise alignment of the dominant and harmonic peaks is observed consistently across all stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$), demonstrating that the interpolated modes ϕ^{μ^*} and eigenvalues s^{μ^*} correctly encode the parameter-dependent dynamics regardless of the choice of initial-condition source. This agreement is as expected in the DMD reconstruction, the neighbouring parameter's initial condition $x_0^{\mu^c}$ influences only the initial modal amplitudes, while the oscillation frequencies and harmonic structure are determined entirely by the eigenvalues and modes [34]. Once the trajectory is phase-aligned, the system rapidly collapses onto the same limit-cycle dynamics, ensuring that the pre-

dicted $C_L(t)$ inherits the correct spectral content even though the initial state originates from a different Reynolds number.

Finally, the predictive capability of the MRPWI framework is evaluated by reconstructing the full-state velocity magnitude field for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$. This reconstruction utilizes the minimal stencil size $N_p = 2$ together with a truncated spectral rank of $r = 20$ in Equation (4.8). As illustrated in Figure (5.13), a side-by-side comparison is presented between the ground-truth velocity magnitude, the MRPWI prediction, and the absolute residual $Residual_{abs}$ error at three distinct times ($\tilde{t} = 255.0, 263.5, 272.0$).

The predicted fields demonstrate high spatiotemporal fidelity, accurately capturing the non-linear evolution and convective transport of the von Kármán vortex street. The sharp gradients within the shear layers and the topology of the alternating vortex cores are preserved with precision, indicating that the interpolated spectral manifold correctly represents the $Re^* = 170$ dynamics. The residual plots (right column) provide a granular view of the reconstruction performance. The maximum pointwise errors are approximately 20% of the peak velocity (peaking at ≈ 0.7645) and are strictly localized in regions of maximum shear and high spatial gradients.

Figure 5.13: Flow reconstruction comparison of *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ at $N_p = 2$.

Specifically, the error is concentrated in three key locations:

- **Near-Wake Shear Layers:** High residuals trace the separation layers immediately downstream

of the cylinder. These zones exhibit the strongest spatial gradients (∇U), so they are hyper-sensitive to even infinitesimal phase mismatches in the interpolated frequency or the initial state.

- **Vortex Core Interfaces:** The residuals manifest as narrow, alternating "dipole" patterns along the upstream and downstream edges of the vortex cores. This suggests that the dominant discrepancy is a slight spatial displacement or "phase jitter" in the positioning of the vortex centers.
- **Roll-up Regions:** The error is most prominent during the initial formation of the vortex cores ($x/L_{\text{ref}} \approx 4$).

Crucially, the absence of diffuse error patterns or large-scale structural distortions confirms that the underlying physics are correctly captured. The localized nature of these residuals indicates that the error is not a physical breakdown of the model, but rather a consequence of using an initial condition $x_0^{\mu_c}$ that originates from a neighboring parameter. While the interpolated modes successfully dictate the global wake topology, the borrowed $x_0^{\mu_c}$ introduces a slight timing offset that manifests as high-frequency jitter at the vortex interfaces. Despite this, the structural integrity of the vortex street is recovered with high fidelity, highlighting the robustness of the phase-aligned spectral manifold.

Figure 5.14: MRPWI prediction error for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

To place these localized residuals in a global context, we examine the corresponding relative L^2 error using Equation (3.1) which is given in Figure (5.14). The error exhibits a prominent initial spike of approximately 20%, which is a direct numerical consequence of the temporal alignment process. The optimal phase lag used for the snapshots alignment is determined via cross-correlation and implemented through a circular shift, the "wrap-around" effect at the $\tilde{t} = 255$ boundary creates a momentary physical mismatch between the reconstructed and true states. However, this transient rapidly decays as the dynamics synchronize, settling into a stable steady-state error of $\approx 7\%$ as shown in the log-scale inset. The fact that the mean error remains nearly constant across $N_p = 2, 4,$ and 6 indicates that the reconstruction accuracy is not limited by the temporal sampling density or stencil size. Instead, the error plateau reflects structural factors inherent to the interpolation setup itself, including the use of a neighboring initial condition $x_0^{\mu_c}$, the truncation to the $r = 20$ coherent modes, and the spacing $\Delta Re = 10$ between the training parameters μ_i . These factors impose a natural error floor that cannot be reduced by increasing N_p . However, the level of agreement achieved with only two training anchors, highlights the robustness of the MRPWI approach in handling oscillatory nonlinear dynamics. It confirms that a topologically coherent spectral manifold enables the smooth and physically consistent transport of complex flow features across the parameter space, providing a reliable surrogate for *unseen* operating conditions.

Noise sensitivity

To examine the robustness of the MRPWI framework under non-ideal conditions, we now repeat the analysis using the same noise injection model introduced previously. As defined in Equation (3.3), the snapshots at each training parameter μ_i are perturbed by a signal scaled Gaussian disturbance whose magnitude is controlled by the prescribed noise level η . In contrast to the earlier noise experiment, the present analysis directly recomputes the DMD operators from the noisy snapshots and therefore the resulting modes and eigenvalues depend on the specific noise realization. For this reason we fix the random seed so that the effect of the interpolation procedure itself can be isolated for a given noisy training dataset. Using the same noise intensities as before, $\eta \in \{10\%, 20\%, 40\%\}$, we recompute the DMD operators, apply the ranking and phase realignment, and evaluate how these perturbations propagate through the MRPWI interpolation procedure at the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

The effects of noise are consistent with the behaviour observed previously for the `ParametricDMD` formulation. Increasing the noise level produces a systematic inward migration of the eigenvalues toward the origin, with the dominant conjugate pair remaining relatively stable while the weak, low-energy modes collapse rapidly. This "eigenvalue shrinkage" becomes more pronounced as η increases and directly explains the damping and loss of coherence observed later in the modal

interpolation.

In Figure (5.15), the relative L^2 reconstruction error during the training window for these three noise levels is shown. As the amount of added noise increases, the reconstruction error rises monotonically: the mean error is approximately 1.11% for 10% noise, 2.24% for 20% noise, and 4.19% for 40% noise. This behaviour is expected, since the perturbation introduced in Equation (3.3) affects both the spatial modes and the associated eigenvalues at the training parameters, leading to a less accurate representation of the noisy snapshots. Nevertheless, the overall error remains low even at 40% noise, indicating that the dominant limit-cycle dynamics are still captured reliably despite substantial contamination of the training data.

To analyse the interpolation step, we begin by considering the accuracy of the modes $\phi_j^{t^*}$. The error defined in Equation (5.1), however, becomes unreliable once noise is added. Even the leading modes can shift noticeably under noise, and the weaker modes are affected even more strongly. Noise can rotate or mix the modes without changing the underlying subspace, so the quantity $\varepsilon_{\text{mode}}(j)$ no longer reflects interpolation accuracy; it mainly measures how much the noisy basis vector has moved relative to the clean reference. Large errors therefore indicate basis rotation rather than interpolation failure, and small errors may occur for accidental reasons. Due to this, modal errors are not a dependable measure in the noisy regime.

Figure 5.15: Reconstruction error of DMD *training* parameter $Re = 160$ after adding noise.

A more reliable approach is to compare the subspaces generated by the modes rather than the individual vectors. Vector level comparisons are unstable in the presence of noise, because small perturbations can rotate a mode by a large angle without changing the subspace it belongs to. In

contrast, the subspace $\text{span}\{\phi_1^{\mu^*}, \dots, \phi_j^{\mu^*}\}$ remains well defined even when the individual modes are noisy, nearly degenerate, or strongly mixed. A subspace-based analysis therefore focuses on the geometry of the dominant invariant structure rather than on any particular choice of basis. This behaviour is well established in subspace perturbation theory, where principal angles provide a basis-independent and noise-robust measure of subspace similarity [17]. Principal angles γ_k between two j -dimensional subspaces are defined as

$$\gamma_k = \arccos(\sigma_k), \quad (5.2)$$

where σ_k are the singular values of $\mathbf{Q}_j^{\mu^* \text{true} \top} \mathbf{Q}_j^{\mu^*}$, and $\mathbf{Q}_j^{\mu^* \text{true}}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_j^{\mu^*}$ are orthonormal bases of the true and interpolated subspaces.

These angles provide a natural, basis-independent, and geometrically meaningful measure of interpolation accuracy. They quantify how much the interpolated subspace $\text{span}\{\phi_1^{\mu^*}, \dots, \phi_j^{\mu^*}\}$ deviates from the true subspace $\text{span}\{\phi_1^{\mu^* \text{true}}, \dots, \phi_j^{\mu^* \text{true}}\}$ without being affected by arbitrary rotations of the individual modes.

The principal angle results reported in Figures (5.16(a), 5.16(c) and 5.16(e)) show a clear and consistent structure across all noise levels and stencil sizes. For the leading modes, the angles remain extremely small (typically well below 1° even at 40% noise). These modes represent the dominant coherent structures of the periodic wake, whose spatial organisation and temporal phase are strongly constrained by the underlying limit cycle. The small principal angles indicate that the geometry of this low-dimensional subspace is only weakly affected by the added noise. As a result, the dominant part of the DMD basis forms a smooth and noise-robust parametric manifold that is well suited for interpolation.

A closer look at the first principal angle shows an approximately linear dependence on the noise amplitude (0.06° at 10% noise, 0.12° at 20% noise, and 0.24°) at 40% noise. This trend demonstrates that the interpolation procedure does not amplify noise and it simply reflects the perturbation present in the training snapshots. The essential limit cycle dynamics and their coherent structures are therefore preserved by the MRPWI framework even under substantial contamination. Beyond the first few modes, the subspace misalignment increases steadily. A transitional region extends roughly from mode $\phi_7^{\mu^*}$ to $\phi_{20}^{\mu^*}$, where the angles grow but remain far from 90° . These modes still carry physical meaning but are more sensitive to noise, as they correspond to weaker eigenvalues and spatial structures with reduced energy. Their parametric variation remains partially coherent, but the associated subspaces become progressively less stable as the noise level increases.

For modes $\phi_j^{\mu^*}$ with $j \gtrsim 20$, the principal angles rise rapidly towards 90° with increasing noise, indicating that these directions are effectively orthogonal across parameters. This behaviour shows that the corresponding modes are dominated by noise and do not form a meaningful parametric

manifold. These high-index modes lie in the weak tail of the DMD spectrum, where the eigenvalues cluster near the origin and the spatial structures lose physical interpretability. Small perturbations in the snapshots cause large rotations in these modes, and their subspaces become uncorrelated across training parameters.

Figure 5.16: Subspace (principal angles) comparison for modes (left column) and eigenvalue interpolation error (right column) for all noise levels and stencil sizes at the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

This behaviour is consistent with the noise-free interpolation results, where a leave-one-out cross-validation across all parameters shows that the dominant subspace remains accurate up to approximately $j \approx 20$. Under added noise, however, only the first $j \approx 15$ modes form a sufficiently stable and noise-robust basis for reliable time-domain reconstruction, as the higher-index modes are more strongly affected by noise. The behaviour of the interpolated eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu*}$ under noise (Figures (5.16(b), 5.16(d) and 5.16(f))) exhibits a clear and structured pattern across all noise levels ($\eta \in \{10\%, 20\%, 40\%\}$) and stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$). In contrast to the modal vectors, which are highly sensitive to perturbations and can undergo large rotations even under small noise, the eigenvalues s_j are scalar quantities and therefore follow classical first-order perturbation theory. Their interpolation errors remain smooth, monotonic, and predictable. For each noise level, the dominant eigenvalues $s_2^{\mu*}, s_3^{\mu*}, \dots$ show very small relative errors, typically in the range $\mathcal{O}(10^{-5})$ – $\mathcal{O}(10^{-2})$, reflecting their well-separated spectral positions and strong dynamical relevance.

A notable exception is the first eigenvalue $s_1^{\mu*} \approx 1$, whose relative error is several orders of magnitude larger than the rest of the spectrum due to its vanishing spectral gap and its role as the neutral direction of the periodic orbit.

Beyond the dominant part of the spectrum, the eigenvalue errors increase gradually with the mode index. Mid-spectrum eigenvalues $s_{10}^{\mu*}, \dots, s_{20}^{\mu*}$ typically exhibit errors of order $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ – $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$, reflecting their reduced energetic content and weaker spectral separation. The tail eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu*}$ for $j > 20$, associated with noise-dominated modes and nearly degenerate spectral components, show the largest errors, often reaching $\mathcal{O}(10^1)$ – $\mathcal{O}(10^2)$. This trend is consistent across all noise levels and stencil sizes, indicating that the weak spectral components do not form a smooth parametric manifold and are inherently difficult to interpolate.

The discrete eigenvalue plots in Appendix Figures (A.10, A.11 and A.12) support these observations. Across all noise levels and stencil sizes, increasing noise pushes the eigenvalues inward toward the origin, with the dominant conjugate pair remaining relatively stable while the weaker modes collapse rapidly. This inward migration becomes more pronounced at higher noise levels, and at 40% noise the spectral tail is almost completely contracted. The stencil size has only a minor influence on the eigenvalue locations, and all three values of N_p produce nearly identical spectra. These plots confirm that the dominant oscillatory dynamics remain robust under noise, while the weak modes lose their physical structure and become highly sensitive to perturbations, consistent with the interpolation error behaviour described above.

To assess how the reconstruction quality manifests in the time domain, we analyse the FFT magnitude spectra of the reconstructed lift-coefficient $C_L^{\mu*}(t)$ using a reconstruction rank of $r = 15$. This choice is consistent with the noise-sensitive behaviour of the modal and eigenvalue spectra, which suggests that only the first $j \approx 15$ modes form a stable and noise-robust basis for reconstruction. Including additional modes (e.g. $r = 20$) introduces noise-dominated components that degrade the

reconstruction and produce spurious spectral artefacts for certain noise levels and stencil sizes.

Figure 5.17: FFT of the True and interpolated lift coefficient C_L for all noise levels and stencil sizes at the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$.

The resulting FFT spectra, shown in Figure (5.17) demonstrate that across all cases the dominant shedding peak is reproduced with excellent accuracy. The frequency remains unchanged and its amplitude aligns closely with the true spectrum, indicating that the MRPWI interpolation preserves the core limit-cycle dynamics even under substantial noise contamination. At 10% noise, the predicted spectra match the true dominant peak almost perfectly, with only minor sideband fluctuations arising from noise in the training snapshots; increasing the stencil size from $N_p = 2$ to $N_p = 6$ yields only slight improvements in suppressing these small-amplitude artefacts. At 20% noise, the dominant peak remains accurately captured for all stencil sizes, while the broadband content and sideband fluctuations increase modestly; again, the influence of N_p is minor, with $N_p = 6$ providing only marginal smoothing. Even at 40% noise, the dominant shedding frequency is still predicted correctly for all values of N_p , although the surrounding spectral structure becomes increasingly distorted by elevated broadband energy and stronger sidebands. Across all noise levels, the choice of stencil size has only a limited effect on the spectral accuracy, and the dominant frequency content is consistently preserved.

The effect of noise on the state reconstruction is quantified in the relative L^2 error curves shown in Appendix Figures (A.13, A.14 and A.15). Across all noise levels and stencil sizes, the reconstruction error remains remarkably stable in time and varies only weakly with N_p . At 10% noise, the mean error is approximately 7.1%, increasing modestly to 7.4% at 20% noise and 8.3% at 40% noise. The close overlap of the curves for different stencil sizes indicates that the interpolation procedure is largely insensitive to the choice of N_p , and that the dominant limit-cycle dynamics are preserved even when the training snapshots are heavily contaminated. The monotonic increase in error with η reflects the degradation of the underlying DMD operators caused by the added noise, but the overall error levels remain low, confirming that the MRPWI reconstruction remains robust across all tested noise intensities.

Overall, the noise sensitivity analysis demonstrates that the MRPWI framework remains remarkably robust under substantial perturbations of the training snapshots. Although noise induces the expected inward drift of weak eigenvalues and causes large rotations of individual modes, the dominant invariant subspace is preserved with high fidelity across all noise levels. Principal angle analysis confirms that this subspace forms a smooth and noise resistant parametric manifold up to approximately $j \approx 20$, while the eigenvalue behaviour shows that only the leading spectral components retain a coherent parametric structure. Consistent with these observations, reliable time-domain reconstruction is achieved using a reduced rank of $r = 15$, which isolates the noise-robust portion of the spectrum. The resulting lift coefficient spectra recover the dominant shedding frequency with excellent accuracy for all stencil sizes and noise intensities, and the relative L^2 reconstruction errors remain low, stable in time, and only weakly dependent on N_p . These findings confirm that MRPWI does not amplify noise and that its interpolation mechanism preserves the essential limit-cycle dynamics even when the training data are heavily contaminated.

5.2 Case study II: Airfoil Flow at High-Speed Stall

5.2.1 Problem setup and model configuration

Figure 5.18: ONERA OAT15A airfoil computational mesh (a) and reduced spatial domain used for the DMD analysis (b).

As a second example for evaluating the method, we consider the transonic buffet problem over the ONERA OAT15A airfoil. This configuration is widely used in aerodynamic reduced-order modelling due to its simple geometry, well-defined boundary conditions, and the presence of self-sustained shock oscillations [20]. Even in two-dimensional simulations, the flow exhibits quasi-periodic shock motion and broadband unsteadiness [40], making it an ideal candidate for reduced-order modelling and spectral analysis [42]. The simulation setup used in this work was provided in the available repository [13], which contains the full configuration, boundary conditions, and sampling strategy used for generating the reference data.

The problem is the simulation of compressible Navier–Stokes flow around an airfoil using the Spalart–Allmaras SALSA turbulence model [12]. The computations are performed with the open-source finite volume framework OpenFOAM, employing its density based compressible solver.

The computational domain Ω consists of a two-dimensional structured O-grid wrapped around an ONERA OAT15A airfoil of unit chord ($c = 1$ m), as shown in Figure (5.18(a)). The grid is extruded with a single cell in the spanwise direction and `empty` boundary conditions are applied on the front and back planes, enforcing a two-dimensional flow. The mesh is strongly clustered near the leading edge, the shock region, and the separated shear layer. The first cell height is chosen to ensure $y^+ < 1$ (where y^+ is the surface normal coordinate in wall units) everywhere on the airfoil surface,

consistent with the wall-resolved requirements of the Spalart–Allmaras SALSA model and standard practice for accurate prediction of shock boundary layer interaction in transonic buffet.

A spatial mask is applied to isolate the dynamically relevant region of the flow. The mask excludes the airfoil surface and the far field while retaining the shock motion, separation bubble, shear layer, and the onset of the wake. The coordinate origin in Figure (5.18(b)) is located at the leading edge of the airfoil, and the blue rectangle shows the corresponding masked region in the (x, z) plane. The simulation is two-dimensional where a single cell is used in the y direction, the modal analysis is performed on the mid-span slice where $y = 0$, so the mask is defined only in (x, z) . In practice, the mask is implemented as a bounding box selecting all grid points within $[-0.15, 2.5] \times [-0.2, 0.75]$. This reduced domain contains 73,803 grid points, ensuring that the extracted modes reflect the buffet dynamics rather than numerical noise or far-field fluctuations.

The simulation is run for a total physical time of $T = 1.0$ s with equispaced time instants $\Delta t = 0.002$ for the field variables, but only the interval $[0.6, 1.0]$ s is written, resulting in 201 snapshots of the flow field for the decomposition. This corresponds to a sampling frequency of $f_s = 500$ Hz, yielding a ratio $f_s/f_b \approx 33$ based on the extracted buffet frequency $f_b \approx 15$ Hz, and a Nyquist limit of 250 Hz. Such oversampling is well within the range identified as safe for avoiding aliasing and ensuring robust DMD mode separation in transonic buffet flows [48].

For the parametric study, the angle of attack α serves as the control parameter. Two *training* parameters μ_i are considered, namely $\alpha = 3.5^\circ$ and $\alpha = 4.5^\circ$, and the DMD operators for each case are constructed from the snapshot range $n \in [300, 500]$ to make sure that the initial transients are excluded from the training (Figure (A.16)). The corresponding spectral quantities $(\Phi^{\mu_i}, S^{\mu_i})$ are then interpolated using the mode realigned point-wise interpolation (MRPWI) algorithm to obtain the prediction at the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0^\circ$.

5.2.2 Mode-Realigned Pointwise Interpolation

To evaluate the results, we begin by establishing an appropriate truncation rank for the DMD operators. The singular values of the snapshot matrix for a *training* parameter α_i (angle of attack) are examined to quantify the energy content captured by the leading modes. The cumulative energy curve shows a rapid decay, with the first two modes already retaining more than 99% of the total energy (Figure (5.19)). Following the same rationale applied throughout this work, we avoid selecting the rank solely from this threshold, since weak but dynamically relevant structures may still reside beyond the 99% cutoff and the smallest singular values tend to be contaminated by numerical noise. To ensure robustness, we adopt a more conservative truncation and a rank of $r = 30$ is selected, which reduces the residual content to approximately $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})$ while avoiding the noise-dominated portion of the spectrum.

Figure 5.19: Cumulative energy of singular values for the snapshot matrix of a *training* parameter α_i .

With the truncation rank fixed at $r = 30$, we assess the accuracy of the DMD model at the training parameters α_i . The relative L^2 reconstruction error, computed according to Equation (3.1), is evaluated over the snapshot interval used for model identification. As shown in Figure (5.20), the error remains bounded and exhibits a periodic pattern consistent with the underlying flow oscillations. The mean value is approximately 0.017%, indicating that the dominant features of the buffet motion are captured with high fidelity by the rank 30 representation. This confirms that the spectral quantities are resolved sufficiently for the subsequent analysis of the unsteady physics.

Figure 5.20: Relative L^2 error for DMD *training* parameter $\alpha = 3.5^\circ$.

Following this reconstruction error assessment, we next examine whether the MRPWI framework

preserves the spectral characteristics of the underlying dynamics at the target *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0$. We compare the continuous-time eigenvalues, s_j , in terms of their real and imaginary components as functions of the mode index j (Figure (5.21(a))). The real parts, $\Re(s_j)$, as we know determines modal growth or decay, show excellent agreement for the dominant modes. Small deviations appear for higher indices, where the interpolated eigenvalues tend to be slightly more negative, indicating a modest increase in predicted damping for the weaker structures. In contrast, the imaginary parts, $\Im(s_j)$, exhibit near-perfect alignment across the entire spectrum. The characteristic alternating pattern associated with conjugate pairs is captured accurately, confirming that the interpolation preserves both the buffet frequency and its higher harmonics.

Figure 5.21: Comparison of continuous-time eigenvalues s_j (a) continuous-time eigenvalues s_j and (b) discrete-time eigenvalues λ_j for the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0^\circ$.

To further assess spectral consistency, the leading discrete-time eigenvalues $\lambda_j = e^{s_j \Delta t}$ are mapped onto the complex plane (Figure (5.21(b))). For the leading buffet modes, the predicted eigenvalues lie almost exactly on the unit circle, reflecting the limit-cycle behavior of the flow. As the mode index increases, both the true and predicted eigenvalues migrate inward, consistent with the increased damping observed in the continuous-time spectrum. The close agreement between the predicted and true eigenvalues across the full arc demonstrates that MRPWI effectively captures the parametric evolution of the system's spectral footprint, even for the higher-frequency modes.

Beyond the spectral alignment, the spatial accuracy of the predicted operator is assessed by comparing the interpolated DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu*}$ for the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0^\circ$ with the true modes $\phi_j^{\mu \text{true}}$. Figure (5.22) presents the real components of the leading modes, where the associated dimensionless frequencies are defined as $\tilde{f} = 2\pi f c / U_\infty$, with c denoting the chord length.

Figure 5.22: Real component of true DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu^{\text{true}}}$ and the interpolated modes $\phi_j^{\mu^*}$ for the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0^\circ$.

Figure 5.23: Phase of true DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu^{\text{true}}}$ and the interpolated modes $\phi_j^{\mu^*}$ for the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0^\circ$.

The fundamental buffet mode, $\phi_1^{\mu^{\text{true}}}$ and $\phi_1^{\mu^*}$ ($\tilde{f} \approx 0.38$), exhibits nearly identical spatial organ-

isation. The predicted mode reproduces the shock–oscillation pattern and the large–scale wake breathing with high fidelity, indicating that the realignment step successfully preserves the dominant coherent structure. As the modal index increases, from the second harmonic ($\phi_3, \tilde{f} \approx 0.77$) through to the fifth ($\phi_9, \tilde{f} \approx 1.92$) the MRPWI interpolation continues to maintain the correct topology and phase distribution. The frequencies remain in excellent agreement, and the spatial phase of the structures is consistently recovered. The remaining discrepancies are confined primarily to local amplitude variations, most notably in the shock–interaction region and in the fine–scale wake features. These differences reflect the reduced parametric smoothness of higher–frequency content rather than a breakdown of the interpolation procedure.

A complementary evaluation is obtained by examining the spatial phase of the DMD modes. Figure (5.23) compares the phase fields $\arg(\phi_j^{\mu^{true}})$ and $\arg(\phi_j^{\mu^*})$ for the same set of dominant buffet modes. In contrast to the real components, the phase comparison reveals substantially larger discrepancies across all modal indices. While the global organisation of the phase in addition to the downstream phase progression and the alternating structure in the wake is broadly preserved, the interpolated modes exhibit clear deviations in regions where the phase varies rapidly.

The most pronounced mismatches occur near the shock foot, along the separated shear layer, and in the far wake. In these regions, even small differences in the complex amplitude lead to significant phase shifts, reflecting the inherent sensitivity of the phase to local flow features. This behaviour is expected as the phase of a DMD mode is defined only up to an arbitrary global rotation and is highly susceptible to perturbations in low–energy regions, making it considerably more challenging to interpolate smoothly across parameters. Despite these discrepancies, the interpolated modes do not display unphysical phase wrapping or discontinuities, and the overall phase topology remains consistent with the true buffet dynamics.

Having assessed both the spatial and phase accuracy of the interpolated modes, we now examine the predictive capability of the reconstructed response. In particular, we evaluate the lift coefficient $C_L^{\mu^*}(t)$ obtained from the MRPWI reconstructed flow field at the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0^\circ$. For consistency with the modal comparison, the signal is analysed in its fluctuation form, i.e., the temporal mean is removed. Figure (5.24) compares the FFT magnitude of the true $C_L^{\mu^{true}}(t)$ and predicted $C_L^{\mu^*}(t)$ signals on both linear and logarithmic scales. As established in literature for two–dimensional shock buffet [14,48], the dominant buffet frequency is recovered with excellent accuracy. Both spectra exhibit a sharp fundamental peak at $St \approx 0.06$, which corresponds to the characteristic St range of $0.05 \leq St \leq 0.1$ reported for periodic shock motion along the chord. The predicted peak location coincides with the true value within the resolution of the discrete transform. The alignment of the peak positions is equally clear in the logarithmic representation, where the fundamental peak remains the most energetic feature and appears at precisely the same St .

Figure 5.24: FFT of the True and interpolated lift coefficient C_L for the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 4.0^\circ$ on linear (top) and logarithmic (bottom) scales.

Beyond the primary peak, the predicted spectrum also reproduces the correct locations of the higher harmonics. On the linear scale, the second and third harmonic peaks appear at the expected multiples of the fundamental Strouhal number ($St \approx 0.12$ and $St \approx 0.18$, respectively), and their positions match those of the true spectrum even when their amplitudes differ slightly. The logarithmic scale further highlights this agreement. The spacing, ordering, and relative placement of the weaker harmonic peaks are preserved across the entire frequency range, demonstrating that the temporal scaling of the unsteady lift response is accurately reconstructed.

The remaining discrepancies are confined to the broadband region and the high-frequency tail, which is expected given the sensitivity of these components to small phase and amplitude errors in the underlying modes.

Since the reconstruction relies on interpolated complex-valued modal coefficients, any local mismatch in the higher-index modes directly influences the fine-scale spectral content of $C_L^{\mu^{true}}(t)$.

Nevertheless, the predicted spectrum retains the correct global structure and accurately reflects the unsteady aerodynamic signature of the buffet dynamics.

To quantify the global accuracy of the temporal reconstruction we look at the relative L^2 error using Equation (3.1) evaluated over the predicted interval (Figure (5.25)). The error evolution displays a clear oscillatory behavior that remains in phase with the lift fluctuations, alternating between approximately 2.5% and 10.8%. The mean reconstruction error is recorded at 7.093%, which represents a high level of fidelity for a parametric prediction at an *unseen* condition in the transonic regime.

Figure 5.25: MRPWI prediction error for the *unseen* parameter $\alpha^* = 170$.

This error level is largely attributed to the aforementioned minor discrepancies in modal amplitudes within the shock-interaction region and the wake. While the dominant buffet frequency and its leading harmonics are captured with high precision (ensuring the physical consistency of the predicted flow field) the cumulative effect of small spatial variations in the high-frequency modes manifests as the observed periodic error. Given that the fundamental dynamics of the shock buffet are inherently sensitive to the parameter α , a mean error below 8% confirms that the MRPWI framework effectively bridges the gap between training snapshots to provide a robust reduced-order representation of the unsteady aerodynamic loads.

6 Summary and conclusions

This work examined the capabilities and limitations of an existing parametric Dynamic Mode Decomposition (pDMD) method for non-linear fluid flows and developed an improved interpolation framework to address the structural deficiencies identified in the baseline method. The investigation proceeded chronologically, beginning with a detailed evaluation of the existing partitioned pDMD implementation, followed by the formulation of a new spectral interpolation strategy, and concluding with a comprehensive validation on two representative flow configurations: laminar cylinder wake dynamics and transonic buffet over an airfoil.

The baseline study revealed that the existing `ParametricDMD` implementation performs exceptionally well at the *training* parameters. The DMD operators extracted from the POD-reduced snapshots produced eigenvalues lying on or near the unit circle, accurately capturing the neutrally stable limit-cycle dynamics of vortex shedding. The reconstructed POD coefficients exhibited excellent agreement with the true trajectories, and the FFT spectra reproduced the correct Strouhal peaks and harmonic content. Spatial reconstructions achieved mean errors below 0.3%, and the forecasting window showed no significant error growth, demonstrating that the DMD operators themselves are stable, physically meaningful, and capable of long-horizon prediction.

However, the method failed catastrophically when applied to an *unseen* parameter. As interpolation is performed directly on POD modal coefficients at each discrete time step, the RBF interpolator blends oscillatory signals with different frequencies and phases. This produces destructive interference, amplitude beating, and spectral splitting, preventing the smooth transport of the dominant shedding frequency across the parameter space. The reconstructed flow fields at $Re^* = 170$ exhibited distorted vortex structures, reversed shear layers, and large spatial residuals. The mean relative error reached 28%, with spikes exceeding 60%. Noise sensitivity analysis further revealed that the POD-based workflow is structurally fragile: perturbations in the snapshots cause eigenvalues to shrink toward the origin, introducing artificial damping and degrading forecasting accuracy. These results demonstrated that POD-coefficient interpolation is fundamentally incompatible with oscillatory systems whose dominant frequencies vary with the parameter.

Motivated by these limitations, a new interpolation strategy was developed based on the principle that parametric dependence should be introduced at the spectral level rather than at the level of time-domain coefficients. The improved algorithm adopts the recently developed mode-realigned pointwise interpolation (MRPWI) framework, which bypasses the POD basis entirely and instead extracts, for each training parameter, the DMD modes $\phi_j^{\mu_i}$ and continuous-time eigenvalues $s_j^{\mu_i}$. These spectral objects are then ranked by integral contribution, conjugate-paired, and phase-realigned using pseudo-angles to eliminate the arbitrary global phase shifts inherent to independent DMD solves. After this alignment, the spectral manifold becomes smooth in parameter space, enabling

one-dimensional Lagrange interpolation on a local stencil of training parameters. In addition to the spectral quantities, the method is extended to interpolate the initial condition $x_0^{\mu_i}$ as well. The resulting triplet $(\Phi^{\mu^*}, S^{\mu^*}, x_0^{\mu^*})$ defines a fully parametric DMD operator at the *unseen* parameter.

A detailed analysis of the initial condition x_0 revealed that, unlike the modes and eigenvalues, it does not vary smoothly with the parameter. Even within the laminar vortex-shedding regime, small phase offsets between limit-cycle snapshots at adjacent Reynolds numbers produced large and unpredictable interpolation errors, with relative L^2 errors fluctuating between $\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$ and $\mathcal{O}(10^0)$ depending on the stencil size and the position of the parameter within the training set. This behaviour deteriorated in the transitional regime, where the instantaneous flow fields changed topology too rapidly for any low-order polynomial to capture. In this range, the curvature of the shear layers, the orientation of the shedding pattern, and the location of vortex roll-up varied in a manner incompatible with a smooth parametric manifold, leading to interpolation errors that reached $\mathcal{O}(10^1)$ for larger stencil sizes. These findings demonstrated that x_0 is not a parametric quantity and cannot be reliably interpolated. A more robust strategy was therefore adopted in which the initial condition is taken from the nearest training parameter and subsequently phase-aligned using cross-correlation of the lift coefficient. This approach decouples x_0 from the parametric interpolation while preserving the correct spectral content of the reconstructed trajectory. Once the interpolated modes and eigenvalues dictate the oscillatory dynamics, the system rapidly collapses onto the correct limit cycle, and the neighbouring initial condition influences only the transient amplitude and phase. The reconstruction achieved high spatiotemporal fidelity, with residuals localized to regions of strong gradients and a stable long-time relative error of approximately 7%. These results confirmed that the MRPWI framework constructs a topologically coherent spectral manifold that enables smooth and physically consistent transport of non-linear oscillatory dynamics across the parameter space.

The noise-sensitivity study further confirmed that the spectral quantities used by MRPWI behave in a structured and predictable manner across all tested noise levels ($\eta \in \{10\%, 20\%, 40\%\}$) and stencil sizes ($N_p = 2, 4, 6$). The dominant eigenvalues and leading modal subspaces remained accurate and coherent, while only the weak, low-energy spectral components showed increased variability. This consistent separation between a stable spectral core and a noise-sensitive tail demonstrates that the interpolation operates on a smooth and robust parametric manifold, ensuring reliable performance even when the training data are substantially perturbed.

The second case study, involving transonic buffet over an airfoil, further validated the generality of the MRPWI framework. Despite the increased complexity of the compressible flow and the presence of shock-induced unsteadiness, the interpolated continuous-time and discrete-time eigenvalues matched the true spectra with high accuracy. The dominant buffet modes were reconstructed with correct spatial topology and frequency content, and the phase fields were preserved across the parameter space. These results demonstrated that the improved algorithm is not limited to laminar

flows but extends naturally to broadband, quasi-periodic, and compressible regimes.

The findings of this work suggest several natural directions for future development. A first avenue concerns the extension of the method to multi-parameter interpolation. In the present study, interpolation was performed in a single parameter only. For the cylinder case, the method was applied to a single *unseen* Reynolds number selected from the *training* parameters, and in the airfoil buffet case only the angle of attack was varied, with too few parameter values to support multi dimensional interpolation. As a result, the spectral manifold remained effectively one-dimensional in both studies. A related open question concerns the behaviour of the method when the *training* parameters exhibit qualitatively different dynamics. In such cases, it is unclear how much parameter-space coverage is required for the spectral manifold to remain coherent, or how many training samples are needed to interpolate reliably between dynamically distinct regimes. Extending the buffet dataset to include variations in both angle of attack and Mach number would provide a more rigorous assessment of the model's generality and reveal how the spectral manifold behaves in regimes where shock motion, separation dynamics, and compressibility effects interact in a strongly non-linear manner. Addressing these issues would clarify the data requirements and the limits of parametric smoothness in realistic aerodynamic applications, where simultaneous variations in angle of attack, Mach number and Reynolds number make the alignment problem substantially more complex.

A second direction concerns a more detailed and systematic analysis of noise. In this work, the random seed was fixed to isolate the effect of the interpolation procedure itself, limiting the interpretation of the results. The variability of weak spectral modes and the structure of their interpolation errors remain unclear, and the influence of the stencil size N_p could not be reliably assessed because the nearest-neighbour initial condition introduced a fixed bias. A more comprehensive investigation involving multiple noise realizations and the true initial condition at the target parameter would clarify the role of N_p and provide a more complete assessment of robustness.

A third direction involves the selection of the reconstruction rank. The LOOCV analysis showed that including more modes does not necessarily improve accuracy; instead, it introduces components that contribute little to the dynamics and degrade both modal and eigenvalue interpolation. This motivates the development of an adaptive rank-filtering strategy that selects the reconstruction rank for the *unseen* parameter based on the parametric smoothness and coherence of the spectral modes rather than on fixed thresholds or cumulative-energy criteria.

A fourth topic concerns the treatment of the initial condition. While nearest-neighbour selection with phase alignment proved effective, a more systematic approach may involve projecting x_0 onto a parameter-dependent subspace or learning a parametric mapping for the modal amplitudes. Such strategies could reduce transient mismatch and improve the consistency of the reconstructed trajectories.

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Appendix

Figures (A.1 and A.2) show the lift-coefficient signals corresponding to all *training* parameters in the 2D cylinder dataset. These signals illustrate the periodic behaviour of the flow and serve as the reference trajectories for the selection of DMD training window.

Figure A.1: Lift coefficient for the first five *training* parameters for the 2D cylinder case.

Figure A.2: Lift coefficient for the second five *training* parameters for the 2D cylinder case.

Figures (A.3–A.5) summarise the influence of noise on the eigenvalue spectra obtained from `ParametricDMD`. For each prescribed noise level, the eigenvalues are shown in the complex plane and compared against the unit circle to illustrate the inward drift of weak modes.

Figure A.3: Eigenvalue spectrum of ParametricDMD *training* parameters at noise level 10%.

Figure A.4: Eigenvalue spectrum of ParametricDMD *training* parameters at noise level 20%.

Figure A.5: Eigenvalue spectrum of ParametricDMD *training* parameters at noise level 30%.

This section presents the interpolation error results for all *training* parameters in \mathcal{P} and for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$. A leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) procedure is used to quantify interpolation accuracy across the entire parameter range. Figures(A.6 and A.7) show the mode and eigenvalue interpolation errors for stencil sizes $N_p = 2, 4, 6$, while the Tables (A.1 and A.2) report the corresponding values.

Figure A.6: Modal and eigenvalue interpolation error for the first five *training* parameters in \mathcal{P} for the 2D cylinder case.

Figure A.7: Modal and eigenvalue interpolation error for the remaining *training* parameters in \mathcal{P} including the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ for the 2D cylinder case.

Table A.1: Mode interpolation error across $Re = 100-200$.

Re = 100			Re = 110			Re = 120		
5	2.5767e-02	1.0894e-02	1.2887e-02	1.6697e-03	1.8162e-03	9.6172e-03	1.1135e-03	7.2623e-04
10	6.1242e-02	3.2286e-02	3.0652e-02	5.2389e-03	5.3899e-03	2.2657e-02	3.4918e-03	2.1524e-03
15	1.1433e-01	4.9273e-02	5.7261e-02	1.2443e-02	1.1704e-02	4.3618e-02	8.2121e-03	4.4128e-03
20	1.6767e-01	1.1468e-01	2.0637e-01	2.9343e-02	3.5775e-02	6.3715e-02	1.9105e-02	1.3752e-02
25	4.0027e-01	9.3012e-01	2.2516e+00	2.4271e-01	4.1229e-01	1.8403e-01	1.5158e-01	1.4666e-01
30	7.0592e-01	2.1089e+00	6.7494e+00	3.7748e-01	1.1748e+00	3.4418e-01	3.3947e-01	4.3388e-01
Re = 130			Re = 140			Re = 150		
5	7.4168e-03	6.7023e-04	5.4464e-04	6.1511e-03	5.0502e-04	2.6917e-04	4.6511e-04	3.0631e-04
10	1.7514e-02	2.1886e-03	1.6144e-03	1.4364e-02	1.5921e-03	8.6125e-04	1.2866e-03	8.2367e-04
15	3.4628e-02	5.2164e-03	3.2920e-03	2.8374e-02	3.8909e-03	2.0684e-03	3.1628e-03	2.0834e-03
20	5.0023e-02	1.2381e-02	1.0318e-02	4.0481e-02	7.9248e-03	6.2995e-03	7.0415e-03	5.6504e-03
25	1.2410e-01	1.0055e-01	1.0999e-01	6.3034e-02	4.7569e-02	6.8070e-02	8.8052e-02	9.7747e-02
30	2.9840e-01	3.0547e-01	3.3237e-01	2.4725e-01	2.5756e-01	2.9094e-01	2.5882e-01	2.8848e-01
Re = 160			Re = 170			Re = 180		
5	4.2302e-03	4.4637e-04	4.4820e-04	3.8915e-03	3.7719e-04	2.7675e-04	3.4871e-04	3.6905e-04
10	9.8473e-03	1.1621e-03	1.0550e-03	8.6279e-03	9.2904e-04	6.3406e-04	8.7971e-04	8.4584e-04
15	1.9754e-02	2.4538e-03	2.0550e-03	1.7049e-02	2.0550e-03	1.3286e-03	2.0151e-03	1.7748e-03
20	2.8627e-02	5.2880e-03	7.2734e-03	2.4650e-02	1.4990e-02	2.0208e-02	3.9059e-02	2.6962e-02
25	1.5747e-01	1.3168e-01	1.3301e-01	9.0584e-02	1.0187e-01	1.2035e-01	8.2471e-02	1.5654e-01
30	2.7072e-01	2.7650e-01	3.0170e-01	2.0600e-01	2.3557e-01	2.7372e-01	2.8048e-01	3.7048e-01
Re = 190			Re = 200					
5	2.7309e-03	5.2312e-04	9.2276e-04	5.4615e-03	2.0927e-03	5.5377e-03		
10	6.0875e-03	1.3203e-03	2.1167e-03	1.2171e-02	5.2855e-03	1.2718e-02		
15	1.2238e-02	3.0244e-03	4.4524e-03	2.4440e-02	1.2122e-02	2.6858e-02		
20	5.1989e-02	5.8547e-02	6.7377e-02	1.0387e-01	2.5479e-01	5.7996e-01		
25	7.8261e-02	1.2561e-01	3.9135e-01	1.5627e-01	5.3542e-01	2.6288e+00		
30	2.8437e-01	3.9451e-01	8.8315e-01	5.4620e-01	1.6424e+00	5.9153e+00		

Table A.2: Eigenvalue interpolation error across $Re = 100-200$.

Re = 100			Re = 110			Re = 120					
Modes	$N_p = 2$	$N_p = 4$	$N_p = 6$	Modes	$N_p = 2$	$N_p = 4$	$N_p = 6$	Modes	$N_p = 2$	$N_p = 4$	$N_p = 6$
5	5.1874e-01	2.3727e+00	5.7082e+00	5	2.5334e+00	5.8003e+00	9.3024e+00	5	2.4851e-01	2.8540e-01	2.7465e-01
10	2.5981e-01	1.1866e+00	2.8549e+00	10	1.2669e+00	2.9002e+00	4.6513e+00	10	1.2444e-01	1.4273e-01	1.3737e-01
15	1.7350e-01	7.9121e-01	1.9038e+00	15	8.4475e-01	1.9335e+00	3.1010e+00	15	8.3083e-02	9.5176e-02	9.1606e-02
20	1.3035e-01	5.9354e-01	1.4282e+00	20	6.3366e-01	1.4502e+00	2.3258e+00	20	6.2403e-02	7.1399e-02	6.8726e-02
25	4.3061e+00	1.8404e+01	4.3964e+01	25	6.0753e-01	1.3742e+00	2.2014e+00	25	9.8642e+00	1.1163e+01	1.0448e+01
30	6.5726e+00	4.0197e+01	1.3483e+02	30	1.8150e+00	5.8398e+00	1.4016e+01	30	8.9037e+00	1.0162e+01	9.3277e+00
Re = 130			Re = 140			Re = 150					
5	4.2301e-01	4.7988e-01	5.0436e-01	5	6.4069e-02	1.0256e-01	2.5951e-01	5	4.6681e-01	4.7761e-01	4.1911e-01
10	2.1158e-01	2.3997e-01	2.5221e-01	10	3.2101e-02	5.1296e-02	1.2977e-01	10	2.3342e-01	2.3881e-01	2.0956e-01
15	1.4111e-01	1.6000e-01	1.6816e-01	15	2.1445e-02	3.4207e-02	8.6525e-02	15	1.5562e-01	1.5920e-01	1.3971e-01
20	1.0587e-01	1.2001e-01	1.2613e-01	20	1.6118e-02	2.5664e-02	6.4903e-02	20	1.1672e-01	1.1941e-01	1.0478e-01
25	1.4000e-01	1.6981e-01	1.8729e-01	25	1.2963e-02	3.8853e-02	8.4078e-02	25	9.6793e-02	9.7551e-02	8.9926e-02
30	8.1264e-01	1.2648e+00	1.7779e+00	30	1.6630e+00	2.1854e+00	2.6535e+00	30	7.2637e-01	9.2915e-01	9.5392e-01
Re = 160			Re = 170			Re = 180					
5	2.0363e-01	2.0144e-01	1.8966e-01	5	3.2404e-03	6.7744e-02	6.8298e-02	5	5.2131e-01	7.0728e-01	1.5141e-01
10	1.0186e-01	1.0074e-01	9.4847e-02	10	1.6443e-03	3.3884e-02	3.4161e-02	10	2.6070e-01	3.5365e-01	7.5718e-02
15	6.7933e-02	6.7178e-02	6.3243e-02	15	1.1122e-03	2.2597e-02	2.2782e-02	15	1.7383e-01	2.3577e-01	5.0489e-02
20	5.0970e-02	5.0394e-02	4.7628e-02	20	8.4689e-04	1.7550e-02	1.7685e-02	20	1.3207e-01	1.7757e-01	3.8619e-02
25	4.4082e-02	4.1084e-02	3.9169e-02	25	4.5294e-03	1.7491e-02	1.7064e-02	25	1.0717e-01	1.4417e-01	3.4973e-02
30	9.8513e-02	4.6512e-01	6.7427e-01	30	6.3619e-01	8.5544e-01	9.5795e-01	30	2.7412e-01	3.0156e-01	2.7087e-01
Re = 190			Re = 200								
5	6.9324e-01	6.8467e-01	2.4429e-01	5	3.2366e-01	6.3902e-01	3.4224e-01				
10	3.4669e-01	3.4234e-01	1.2218e-01	10	1.6196e-01	3.1953e-01	1.7133e-01				
15	2.3117e-01	2.2823e-01	8.1480e-02	15	1.0806e-01	2.1304e-01	1.1436e-01				
20	1.7458e-01	1.7230e-01	6.3010e-02	20	8.3582e-02	1.6455e-01	9.7860e-02				
25	1.4077e-01	1.4119e-01	6.1279e-02	25	6.9237e-02	1.4604e-01	1.4864e-01				
30	1.6128e+00	1.1499e+01	2.4889e+01	30	3.9741e-01	4.0070e+00	1.3112e+01				

Figure (A.8) shows the initial conditions associated with the laminar *training* parameters. The corresponding relative L_2 interpolation errors for $N_p = \{2, 4, 6\}$ are listed in Table (A.3). These results quantify how well the initial state can be interpolated across $Re = 100$ –200.

Figure A.8: Initial condition x_0 of *training* parameters.

Figure (A.9) shows the initial conditions for the transition-regime *training* parameters. Table (A.4) reports the corresponding relative L_2 interpolation errors for $Re = 400$ –500 and $N_p = \{2, 4, 6\}$.

Table A.3: Relative L_2 error for interpolation across $Re = 100\text{--}200$ and $N_p = \{2, 4, 6\}$.

Re	$N_p = 2$	$N_p = 4$	$N_p = 6$
100	3.36e-01	7.15e-01	2.15e+00
110	1.52e-01	1.62e-01	3.24e-01
120	1.23e-01	9.87e-02	1.19e-01
130	1.01e-01	8.08e-02	8.19e-02
140	9.30e-02	7.01e-02	6.81e-02
150	8.70e-02	6.45e-02	6.13e-02
160	8.63e-02	6.65e-02	6.33e-02
170	9.31e-02	7.45e-02	7.34e-02
180	1.10e-01	9.01e-02	9.21e-02
190	1.39e-01	1.28e-01	2.18e-01
200	2.64e-01	4.85e-01	1.24e+00

Figure A.9: Initial condition x_0 of *training* parameters in the laminar regime.

Table A.4: Relative L_2 error for interpolation across $Re = 400\text{--}500$ and $N_p = \{2, 4, 6\}$.

Re	$N_p = 2$	$N_p = 4$	$N_p = 6$
400	9.10e-01	3.52e+00	1.29e+01
410	4.44e-01	8.57e-01	2.09e+00
420	5.23e-01	5.56e-01	8.14e-01
430	5.45e-01	6.00e-01	5.97e-01
440	5.10e-01	5.78e-01	5.94e-01
450	5.31e-01	6.21e-01	6.61e-01
460	5.95e-01	7.19e-01	7.87e-01
470	6.31e-01	7.84e-01	8.78e-01
480	6.29e-01	7.94e-01	1.15e+00
490	6.05e-01	1.17e+00	2.81e+00
500	1.19e+00	4.58e+00	1.66e+01

Figures(A.10–A.12) show the interpolated eigenvalue spectra at the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ for noise levels 10%, 20%, and 40%. These plots illustrate how noise affects the stability and clustering of the interpolated eigenvalues.

Figure A.10: Interpolated eigenvalue spectrum of *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ using MRPWI at noise level 10%.

Figure A.11: Interpolated eigenvalue spectrum of *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ using MRPWI at noise level 20%.

Figure A.12: Interpolated eigenvalue spectrum of *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ using MRPWI at noise level 40%.

Figures(A.13–A.15) present the MRPWI reconstruction error at $Re^* = 170$ for the noise levels 10%, 20%, and 40%. These curves show the time-domain accuracy of the interpolated model under increasing perturbation.

Figure A.13: MRPWI prediction error for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ at noise level 10%.

Figure A.14: MRPWI prediction error for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ at noise level 20%.

Figure A.15: MRPWI prediction error for the *unseen* parameter $Re^* = 170$ at noise level 40%.

Figure (A.16) shows the lift-coefficient signals for *training* parameters in the ONERA OAT15A buffet dataset. These signals form the basis for the selection of DMD training window in the transonic regime.

Figure A.16: Lift coefficient for the *training* parameters for the ONERA OAT15A airfoil case.

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die von mir am heutigen Tag der Professur für Strömungsmechanik eingereichte Masterarbeit zum Thema

Dynamic mode decomposition for parametric fluid flow modeling

vollkommen selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt, sowie Zitate kenntlich gemacht habe.

Dresden, 29. April 2026

Haseeb Amjad